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Demystifying Rhetorical Persuasion Used by Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns

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Abstract

This study aimed to unveil and explore the common linguistic features and persuasive techniques used by Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns. The categories of linguistic features were referred to Finegan's Language Structure and Use (2008). Using a discourse analysis approach, the research focused on three main dimensions: morphology, semantics, and syntax. Ten (10) videos of speeches in Sangguniang Kabataan were gathered from both Facebook and YouTube. Within the domain of morphology, the study revealed that out of the ten (10) speeches analyzed, all of them used compounding and initialisms. In the realm of semantics, the analysis uncovered common terms frequently used by Sangguniang Kabataan. In terms of syntax, the analysis reveals that ten out of six speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan used simple sentences, four used compound sentences, five complex sentence and three used compound-complex sentences. On the other hand, categories of persuasive strategies were referred to in Lamb's Theory (2013). The result of the analysis showed the distribution as follows: five data on repetition, five data on inclusive words, five data on emotive language, five inclusive words, five data on generalization, five data on colloquial language, four data on connotation, four data of hyperbole, six data of imagery, five data of rhetoric question, two data of anecdotes, five data of simile and five data of appeals.

Keywords: *linguistic features, rhetoric, persuasive strategies, sangguniang kabataan, discourse analysis, Philippines*

Introduction

In the world of politics, persuasive strategies are utilized in the communication process to influence, convince, justify, and negate people. By focusing on the stylistic features of political speeches, such as vocabulary use, sentence structure, and figurative language, this study provides a deeper understanding of how politicians use language to convey their messages and persuade their audience. Furthermore, negative persuasion it involves using language to influence people, deceiving or using negative words against other parties which lead to doubts or skepticism in audience's mind and inappropriate strategy. Political speeches are an important mode of communication that can shape public opinion, influence policy decisions, and affect the outcomes of elections (Hoggan & Aloni, 2020; Sravani et al., 2021).

In the global context, particularly in US campaigns the partisan perceives a negative ad from the opposition party in order to be less persuasive and less agreeable than negative ads from their side. However, both parties addressed negative information and shows negative massive attack against each other during the last few weeks of the election such as criticizing and deceiving, both camps launched strong, sometimes anonymous, personal attacks in newspapers or secretly funded pamphlets. Therefore, it has become a significant concern in politics, posing challenges to social harmony and it address negative aspects of the targeted to neutralize the negative tone and negative information (Haselmayer, 2020)

In the Philippine context, there were two parties during the election most were coveted for a position for councilors, due to the same interest of both parties, they fought one another for a position using rhetorical strategies such as striking, deceiving against other opponent parties, and using powerful words to persuade the people. Therefore, among those recognized political parties their dilemma during election campaigns which covered with a lot of controversies (Vallejo, 2022).

Moreover, a study should be conducted that focuses to the analysis of persuasive expressions and linguistic strategies employed by young politicians to influence the audience or voters. The study holds significant social relevance it lies in its potential to help citizens or voters to understand the rhetorical and linguistic strategies used by Sangguniang Kabataan during the election campaigns, empowering them to critically analyze political discourse. Also aims to illustrate how language is interpreted differently across speech communities. In relation to this, such a study is sufficiently urgent and have significant role for young politicians by promoting effective youth engagement and participation. It contributes to the development and well-being of local communities, addressing relevant issues and fostering leadership skills among the youth. By investigating the language features and persuasive techniques used by Sangguniang Kabataan, the research seeks to benefit the general public and contribute to increasing the number of youths in public service.

In connection, a large number of studies supporting discourse analysis, it has been rarely used to analyze political campaign rhetoric through time. A study conducted by Salih and Dawn which entitled "Overt and Covert Persuasion: A Rhetorical Analysis approach to the language of advertisements and Election Campaigns" mainly focused on the effectiveness of linguistic persuasive style in influencing or to convince the people in order to change their attitudes or perspective. On the other hand, a study conducted by Khajavi which entitled "A Discourse Analytic Investigation into Politicians 'Use of Rhetorical and Persuasive Strategies: The Case of US election speeches; mainly focused on the rhetorical and persuasive strategies in the political speeches. Although these studies may exist, none of them looked into political election campaigns used by Sangguniang Kabataan. Additionally, the study that would be conducted it focuses on how the linguistic features and what are the persuasive or techniques words they are going to use during the

election campaigns. This study would be used as extra research for academics who would be interested in this issue.

Finally, the results will not only cultivate the classification of persuasive strategies in the campaigns but also widen its perspective and proper utilization in the context of election campaigns. Subsequently, the findings will be disseminated through publishing the study in the reputable academic journals focused on persuasive strategies and young politicians' well-being. Also, the results of this study will be presented at local and regional educational conferences to share insights and gather feedback from peers. Consequently, by combining publication in a peer-reviewed journal with presentations at academic conferences, the researcher aimed to reach a broad audience of educators and researchers, helping to address the problems discussed and implement the suggested recommendations.

Research Questions

This research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the linguistics features found in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns?
2. What are the rhetorical persuasion strategies present in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design utilizing a discourse analysis approach to explore and understand the subjective experiences and perceptions of individuals and groups. Qualitative research involves a process of inquiry that encompasses the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data to comprehend social phenomena in their natural contexts. It is characterized by its emphasis on context and flexibility, qualitative research employs various methods to generate rich, detailed data. This approach is particularly valuable for revealing linguistic features and persuasive strategies within communication. Ultimately, the goal of qualitative research is to understand and interpret social phenomena through the exploration of in-depth, nuanced, and context-specific data (Moajan, 2018).

This study adopted a qualitative research design, as it was the most suitable for examining the rhetorical and persuasive techniques used in Sangguniang Kabataan. Since all politicians have various ways during their speech, a qualitative approach provided the flexibility needed to capture these shifting persuasive strategies and explore new trends as they emerged. It also allowed for a contextual understanding of how persuasion worked in this space, taking into account factors like during election campaigns, to the target audience, and the social environment. Additionally, qualitative design also captured the richness of real-world language used in during election campaigns. It facilitated the discovery of unexpected findings and supported a deep engagement with data, uncovering layers of meaning. It also aims to understand and interpret social phenomena through the exploration of in-depth, nuanced, and context-specific data it can help increase current understanding of unexplored aspects of a subject. Lastly, it encouraged reflexivity, promoting transparency and credibility in the analysis (Mohajan, 2018).

Moreover, this study employed a discourse analysis approach. Discourse analysis is a method used in the fields of linguistics, communication studies, disciplines. Investigating both oral and written language to understand how language is used in communication, and it focuses on analyzing not just individual words or sentences, but entire texts. Researchers used this approach to examine the structure, context, and social implications of language to uncover underlying meanings, ideologies, and power dynamics in communication. Furthermore, it can be applied to various types of discourse, such as political speeches, interviews, advertisements or everyday conversations and it aims to understand how language is used in real life situations. Thus, it examines larger linguistic units as conversational exchanges of written and spoken text (Abdullahi et al., 2020).

Using discourse analysis as the research method in this study allowed for a comprehensive examination of the linguistic features and persuasive strategies employed in Sangguniang Kabataan. This method played a crucial role in uncovering the persuasive elements embedded in the discourse. Additionally, discourse analysis enabled the exploration of how language was used to convey credibility and authority, enhancing the overall understanding of its rhetorical impact. The approach facilitated the examination of a large collection of language data, which made it possible to identify the frequency of specific language forms, their contexts of use, and the linguistic properties contributing to their meanings. This method provided valuable insights into both the linguistic and social factors that shape language use, revealing patterns that might remain hidden in smaller language samples. As a result, discourse analysis proved to be an invaluable tool for gaining a deeper understanding of the meaning, function, and usage of language in speeches, allowing for a nuanced exploration of the strategies employed in the communication of ideas and influence.

Instrument

As such, this study utilized ten (10) speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan. The researcher utilized social media (Facebook and YouTube) as the source for collection of corpora, where the linguistic features and persuasive techniques were found. Evidently, Braun and Clarke (2003) made some suggestions on the number of research materials to be utilized. As an anchor, it had previously been recommended at this study required a minimum sample size of at least 10-100 research materials as sources to sufficiently fulfill the goal of the study and reach the data saturation. Therefore, ten (10) videos of Sangguniang Kabataan were deemed sufficient for this study to be undertaken.

The following would be the criteria for selected research materials, ensuring a comprehensive and focused collection for analysis (a) The speeches must have been original from the Sangguniang Kabataan (b) The duration of speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan maximum of one (1) hour (c) must be the speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan happen 2021 up until the present (d) speeches gathered by watching videos and personal recorded to the Sangguniang Kabataan politician during election campaigns. The research corpora underwent content analysis. The focus was on how the Sangguniang Kabataan used language as a strategy as well as to unveil their rhetoric persuasive techniques.

The researcher reviewed and transcript the video that were collected. In order to obtain the target number of corpora, the researcher must be chosen carefully and follow predetermined timeline according to established criteria. The corpora were named or coded to simply tracking the research materials SK-01 and followed, until its reached SK-10.

Procedure

A researcher took series of steps in collecting the data and other viable information relevant to the study. Before conducting the study, the researcher asked first her adviser to know the steps that were needed to be taken in accomplishing this research. Since the researcher and the adviser could work together in order to emphasize the necessary things for completing the research study. On the other hand, the series of steps in conducting were followed to ensure that the process of the data collection adhered to the principles and ethical standard. Thus, the researcher carefully designed the research methodology, selecting appropriate data collection methods and sampling techniques. Certainly, this study involved considering ethical considerations such as informed consent, confidentiality, and the protection of collected data.

Moreover, utilizing the discourse analysis approach represented a new experience as a researcher. A series of questions was prepared to ask the research adviser regarding the entire study process. It is essential to possess sufficient knowledge about the chosen method to ensure the comprehensiveness of the study.

The researcher selected ten (10) speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) during election campaigns. Then, the researcher gathered and analyzed the relevant data needed in the study. The data that collected were subject to treatment and interpretation. To have a vivid view of the research undertaken, the relevant information presented in the following chapters.

Lastly, the results were carefully presented and discussed. The information was analyzed, explored, and treated respectfully based on the problem of the study.

Data Analysis

To investigate the research questions, the study employed a qualitative research design, analyzing a corpus of ten (10) Sangguniang Kabataan speeches posted from YouTube and Facebook. The selection of these videos was guided by specific criteria aligned with the research objectives. As the primary data analyst, the researcher utilized discourse analysis to explore the linguistic and rhetorical strategies within the specific context of these speeches.

The analysis process was anchored in the theoretical frameworks discussed in the first chapter, specifically the language use and structure proposed by Finegan (2008) and the rhetoric theory of Lamb (2014). These frameworks informed the data analysis as sought to address the research questions.

Finegan's (2008) theoretical framework guided the examination of linguistic features in the Sangguniang Kabataan speeches, focusing on three key aspects: morphology, semantics, and syntax. In the morphological analysis, researcher identified various word formations, including affixation, reduplication, compounds, and shortening (such as acronyms, initialisms, and blends), as well as backformation and neologisms. The semantic analysis examined occurrences of hyponyms, synonyms, antonyms, polysemy, homonymy, and metaphorical expressions. Additionally, the syntactic analysis considered the presence of simple, compound, complex, and compound-complex sentences.

Lamb's (2014) rhetoric theory provided insights into the second research question, outlining 25 persuasive techniques employed in the speeches. These techniques included alliteration, analogy, anecdote, appeals, assonance, attacks, clichés, connotation, emotive language, everyday/colloquial language, euphemism, evidence, hyperbole, generalization, expert opinion, inclusive language, imagery, jargon, logic/reason, metaphor, pun, repetition, rhetorical question, sarcasm, and simile.

As the primary data analyst for this study, the researcher systematically applied these theoretical frameworks to interpret and analyze the persuasive strategies utilized by the speakers, thereby answering the research questions and contributing to a deeper understanding of the rhetorical landscape within these election campaign speeches.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure proper practice and conduct of the study, the ethical codes considered and followed which observed and apply towards the implementation of this study. These are the following: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent, and confidentiality (Mac et al., 2005).

The first principle, respect for persons, is an important ethical consideration in corpus-based research, requiring the researchers to

acknowledge the autonomy and dignity of individuals who were the subjects of their research. This included obtaining informed consent, protecting privacy and confidentiality, and avoiding exploitation or coercion of research participants. It is also highlighted the importance of obtaining informed consent from participants and protecting their privacy and confidentiality, as well as ensuring that the data is anonymized and could not be traced back to individual participants (Mack et al., 2005).

In the absence of direct participants in her study, the researcher successfully adhered to ethical principles by ensuring that all data utilized in her research was properly cited. This commitment to transparency not only upholds academic integrity but also respects the intellectual property of the original authors. Additionally, she took critical steps to protect personal information by removing or anonymizing any identifying details during the transcription and analysis process. This practice is essential for safeguarding participants' confidentiality, even when they are not actively involved in the research.

Moreover, the researcher rigorously followed established data-gathering techniques in line with the guidelines set forth by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) and the panel of examiners. By doing so, she ensured that her methodology was not only appropriate but also ethically sound. Her clear and transparent description of the research methodology, alongside an acknowledgment of potential ethical concerns and limitations, illustrates a commitment to upholding the autonomy and dignity of individuals. This careful attention to ethical considerations reflects a broader responsibility in the research community, emphasizing that ethical research practices are paramount, regardless of whether human participants are directly involved. The researcher's proactive measures highlight the importance of maintaining ethical standards and fostering trust in the research process, ultimately contributing to the credibility and reliability of her findings.

The second principle, beneficence, involved doing good and promoting the welfare of others. In corpus-based research, beneficence required that researchers aimed to promote the well-being of those affected by their research. This includes ensuring that the research did not cause harm and that any potential benefits were maximized. Arifin (2018) discussed the need to balance the potential benefits of the research with the potential risks or harms to the community being studied. The researcher took steps to minimize any potential harms and maximize the potential benefits, such as by sharing the research findings with the community or involving community members in the research process.

In this study, the researcher utilized corpora strictly for academic research purposes, emphasizing a commitment to ethical standards in the treatment of individuals represented within the materials, ensuring their well-being is paramount and that the use of such materials does not result in harm or insult. The analysis was specifically designed to yield results that would significantly benefit individuals, particularly those aspiring to become female politicians, by focusing on their experiences and perspectives to provide valuable insights and support for women navigating the political landscape. This approach underscores the ethical and constructive intent of the research, prioritizing the welfare of the subjects while striving to generate positive impacts on their aspirations and endeavors in politics. By adhering to ethical considerations and focusing on constructive outcomes, the study contributes to the broader discourse on gender representation and empowerment in politics.

The third principle, justice, demands a fair distribution of the risks and rewards as a consequence of the research. It is crucial to recognize everyone's contributions because all participants contribute to the research's achievement in some way. In all the researcher's endeavors, she gives proper credit. During the study, participants are unable to spend any money. Therefore, as a way of gratitude for the participants' contributions to the study, sensible tokens are given to them. Through this study, the researcher hopes that the participants freed from any unpleasant memories they may have and preserve a positive reputation for any useful insights they may provide (Mack et al., 2005).

In the current research, even though the study did not involve human participants, the researcher still ensures fairness and equity in the study by obtaining permission to use the corpus data and adhering to any relevant copyright or usage restrictions. The researcher also ensures that the corpus data is anonymized and confidential, particularly in cases where it contains sensitive or personal information. Moreover, to avoid bias, the researcher selects a representative sample of the notable women speeches and ensures that the analysis is based on objective criteria. Additionally, the researcher was transparent in documenting the methods and procedures used in the study to ensure reproducibility. Furthermore, the researcher also reported any limitations or potential biases in the study and provides a balance and nuance interpretation of the findings to ensure fairness and equity. By adhering to these ethical principles, the researcher ensured that the study is conducted in an ethical and responsible manner, even if there are no human participants involved.

The last principle, confidentiality, is an ethical consideration in corpus-based research that involves protecting the privacy and anonymity of individuals whose language is being analyzed. In the context of the corpus-based thesis, confidentiality refers to protecting the identity of individuals who have contributed to the corpus data. Dr. Allen discussed the ethical implications of using language data in research, particularly in relation to issues of confidentiality and anonymity. She emphasizes the importance of respecting the privacy of individuals whose language is being analyzed and suggested methods for anonymizing corpus data to ensure confidentiality (Allen, 2017).

In this study, although it did not directly involve human participants, the researcher took significant steps to maintain confidentiality and protect the privacy of the individuals whose language data was being analyzed. One key measure was anonymization removing or altering any identifying information that could potentially link the language data back to its original source. This was done to ensure

that the identities of the language users remained hidden, preserving their anonymity.

In addition to anonymizing the data, the researcher sought permission to use the corpus and complied with all relevant copyright and usage regulations. This was an important step to ensure that the data was being handled ethically and responsibly. To further safeguard the data, the researcher implemented strict security measures to prevent unauthorized access or misuse. The data was stored securely and only shared with individuals who were authorized to work with it. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher ensured that the privacy of the individuals whose language was analyzed was respected at all times, even though no direct human subjects were involved in the study. This approach reflects a strong commitment to maintaining ethical standards in research, regardless of the nature of the data being used.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the gathered data taken from Speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Election Campaigns. The speeches were transcribed, scrutinized, and analyzed to identify the linguistic features and persuasive strategies. The data that was collected to answer the two research questions; first, what are the linguistics features of Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns? Second, what are the rhetorical persuasion strategies present in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns? This part of the paper presented the linguistic features of the Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns, particularly the morphological and semantic features. This chapter also presented the rhetorical persuasion strategies employed in the Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns.

Research Question 1: What are the linguistics features of Sangguniang Kabataan?

In this part delves into what are the linguistics features of Sangguniang Kabataan. The analysis was viewed upon the Language Use and Structure of Finegan (2008) who emphasizes that words are the main point of language. He also believes that when examining language, words are the main focus since language is built around words. Finegan starts looking at language by considering words from different perspectives, such as morphology, semantics, and syntax.

Morphological Features in Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns

Morphology is the study of the structure and form of words in a language, including the way they are constructed, their roots words, prefixes, suffixes, and how they combine to create meaning and it studies the relationship between morphemes, and how morphemes can be put together to create new words, or new forms of the stem word. Understanding how the words were formed enables us to unlock our vocabulary, particularly on what words we must use to create a meaningful and effective communication as well as it is analyzing the structure of words, phrases, and sentences necessitates an understanding of how these structures are employed in everyday social exchanges. Therefore, it is crucial to recognize that languages offer multiple approaches to express identical ideas and to assess how these alternatives effectively achieve social and communicative objectives.

The analysis was made by the researcher on the Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns, and it was found out that there were types of morphological process present in the Speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns. The collected data were analyzed based on Lamb's Lexicon and Morphological Features.

The morphological feature focused on how words can be dissected such as making of new words from existing words, get words from different dialects and make new words simply by utilizing their inventive personalities. The morphological features in Sangguniang Kabataan were analyzed in a tabular presentation which points out different processes such as derivational morpheme, inflectional morpheme, compounding, and initialisms.

To delve deeper into the details, each category is carefully examined. The derivational morpheme table provides insights into the process, code, and sample statements. Similarly, the inflectional morpheme table outlines the process, function of the affix, and corresponding sample statements. Furthermore, the textual discussions are dedicated to elucidating the words presented in the matrices. By referring to Table 1.1.1, the study reveals a comprehensive compilation of words used in Sangguniang Kabataan speeches. These words undergo a derivational process, which entails changes in lexical category. Additionally, sample statements exemplify this morphological aspect.

In linguistic morphology, it is focused on studying words formation and how it relates to other words in language. The experts in language studies the words and its componential parts to learn its structure and the meaning that the particular words possessed. Derivational morpheme can be classified as an affix. An affix is a group of letters that cannot stand on its own or a bound morpheme. Prefix is a type of affix that added to the beginning of the word, while suffix is a group of letters that are added at the end of a word.

Derivational morpheme. Is a morpheme added to a word to create a new word with a different meaning and function. It typically changes the grammatical category or the meaning of the base word. In grammar, derivational morpheme is an affix which group of letters added, the (prefix) is the beginning, while "suffix" is after the end or referring as the root or base word to create a new word or a new form of an existing word. However, upon examining the speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan, it was observed that such words also undergo this transformative process. Also, derivational morphemes have the ability to expand vocabulary, convey grammatical relationships, express attitudes, organize texts, and reveal language change makes them invaluable tools for understanding the nuances of communication.

Furthermore, the addition of derivational morpheme to a word resulted in the changes of lexical category of the root word or the free morpheme. The result of this morphological process calls derivatives or the derived words. Derivational process only changes the lexical category but not the meaning of the word. Derivational morphemes added on words are not limited to one morpheme. Multiple morphemes can be added to a single root word, depending on its intended use or produce a multiple variety of meanings. In order to give an emphasis or precise meaning to an intended usage of words, adding a morpheme might be in the beginning, or in the end of a word must be adhered.

As presented in Table 1.1.1 below, the study found the complete presentation of the words embedded in Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns which undergone a derivational process as morphological aspect. The table also included the process of how the root word changed its lexical category, from noun to adjective, adjective to adverb, verb to noun, and noun to verb. The sample statements or the corpora where the derivational process have been found were also included. The bold word in the sample statement indicates that the word undergone derivational processed.

Table 1.1.1. *Derivational Morphemes*

<i>Derivational Morpheme</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>
Noun to Adjective	<p>“Barangay Población will be even better, livelier, and more beautiful in a good way” SK-05</p> <p>“I will be transparent with all the budgets allocated for my projects, providing receipts or documents, because I am honest and faithful to the youth and our barangay” SK-07</p>
Adjective to Adverb	<p>“According to them, education is the most powerful weapon that we can use to change the world” SK-10</p> <p>“I don't want to focus solely on one sport like basketball; other sports should be included so everyone can benefit” SK-06</p> <p>“I will collaborate with my father, Dennis Ermitano, who is also running for barangay captain, towards progress, happiness, and peace. And most importantly, to foster unity for the development of our barangay” SK-07</p> <p>“This effectively imparts to youth opportunity and that will be the ways for their improvement or resilient youth's idea” SK-03</p>
Verb to Noun	<p>“Before I became business manager in NYCM, or New Corella Youth Movement” SK-01</p> <p>“I am also a player and I am witnessed that sports are one of the things that shape the mentality and strategies that can help a person's personality” SK-07</p> <p>“We will elect officer for each event, not only acquaintances or relatives should handle the event but also others should be given a chance” SK-08</p>
Noun to Verb	<p>“People in barangay Poblacion, both team Suluguon and the team Buagas, are ready to listen” SK-05</p> <p>“This ceasefire agreement should be unconditional as it benefit both parties to the conflict and help the threaten citizens” SK-06</p> <p>“May his memory light up the fire within us and strengthen ourselves to become patriots” SK-08</p>

As presented in the Table above, derivational morpheme was found in the Sangguniang Kabataan's speeches. In the statement the word “beauty” is a noun when attached by a bound morpheme or suffix “ful”, it became “beautiful”. Therefore, the bound morpheme “ful” attached to a noun it changes the lexical category of the new form words, from noun to adjective. Here's the complete sample statement.

“Barangay Población will be even better, livelier, and more beautiful in a good way” (SK-05)

Moreover, another derivational morpheme was found in the gathered corpora. The word ‘faith’ is a base form and a noun and when the bound morpheme ‘-ful’ is attached to, a new word ‘faithful’ is formed. This particular transformation is one of the best examples of how derivational morphemes work; or how otherwise they bring about change in both meaning and category of a word. Therefore, the word ‘faithful’ changes its status into an adjective which means a semantic transition from concept domain to thing/un thing or object domain. Here's a sample statement to demonstrate the usage:

“I will be transparent with all the budgets allocated for my projects, providing receipts or documents, because I am honest and faithful to the youth and our barangay” (SK-07)

Besides that, there was another derivational morpheme found in the gathered corpora which were assembled. The English word “Power” is actually an uninflected form and when this has been compounded with bound morpheme/suffix “ful” we have another noun in English language that is “Powerful” However, this is how the below explains the transition that we saw the root words move from being just this lexical category by attaching a derivational morpheme from a noun to make it an adjective. Included below is a sample statement:

“According to them, education is the most powerful weapon that we can use to change the world” (SK-10)

Aside from that, other derivational morphemes were identified in the gathered corpora. A derivational morpheme is one that changes meaning of the base word. For instance, while the word “sole” is an adjective, then after adding the suffix “-ly;” it becomes “solely.” Originally, the word is recognized as the adjective, but when adding the morpheme “-ly” attached to the word, it becomes the adverb “solely”. It explains how derivational morphemes modify root words switching over the lexical category and their inherent versatility in grammatical roles. Below is the sample statement from the gathered corpora.

“I don't want to focus solely on one sport like basketball; other sports should be included so everyone can benefit” (SK-06)

Another, derivational morpheme was found in the gathered corpora, can be identified in the process of changing the words “important”. Important as an adjective is a word that is usually placed in front of a noun to give more information or description on the noun in question. When suffix “-ly” is added the term which comes out is “importantly”, and this changes the part of speech from an adjective to that of an adverb. This shows how derivational morpheme is capable of changing the word class in order to do distinct grammatical function in a sentence. The complete sample statement is in the following.

“I will collaborate with my father, Dennis Ermitano, who is also running for barangay captain, towards progress, happiness, and peace. And most importantly, to foster unity for the development of our barangay” (SK-07)

In the other words, whereas in linguistic analysis derivational morphemes play a central role in changing the lexical category of a word. For example, when the derivational suffix is “-ly” is applied on the adjective “effective, the outcome will be the adverb “Effectively”. Not only does it change the inference of the word under consideration, but also creates a new grammatical function of the word in a particular sentence. Therefore, that such transformations demonstrate the specific use and significance of the morphemes to the language's flexibility and richness. The complete sample statement is the following:

“This effectively imparts to youth opportunity and that will be the ways for their improvement or resilient youth's idea” (SK-03)

Apart from that, derivational morpheme like from verb to noun was also manifested in the analyzed corpora. The word with a lexical category of verb attached by morpheme “er” at the end, derives new words and new lexical category which is noun. The word “play” is verb when attached by “er” became “player”. The derived word has new lexical category from verb to noun. Below is the sentence that this derivational process was found when the corpora was analyzed.

“I am also a player and I am proof that sports are one of the things that shape the mentality and strategies that can help a person's personality” (SK-07)

In addition, in the Sangguniang Kabataan speech mentioned above the word ‘manages’ also is a verb. That is why the term ‘manager’ originates from the word by adding the suffix ‘-er’ to the end of it. Such a change is made to provide enough grounds for the shift, which has been revealed in the lexical category, from the verb into the noun. The word derivation process also means that the word derives not only a different form but also a different function in a sentence. Here's the complete statement below.

“Before I became business manager in NYCM, or New Corella Youth Movement” (SK-01)

Moreover, a word “office” is a lexical category of verb when it attached by suffix “er” transform into “officer”. Therefore, the derived word has new lexical category from verb to noun. This show on how the root words changed in lexical category through attachment of derivational morpheme. Below is sample statement that this derivational process was found when the corpora was analyzed.

“We will elect officer for each event, not only acquaintances or relatives should handle the event but also others should be given a chance” (SK-08)

Aside from that, another derivational morpheme that found in the gathered corpora was the word with lexical category of a noun attached by morpheme or a suffix “en” derives verb word. The word “list” is a lexical category of noun when added with a suffix “en” derives a new word “listen. Therefore, this show on how the root words changed in lexical category through attachment of derivational morpheme. This is the sample statement that unveiled this derivational process in the corpora.

“People in barangay Poblacion, both team Sulugon and the team Buagas, are ready to listen “(SK-05)

Furthermore, another derivational process that can be found in the corpora was the word with lexical category of a noun attached by morpheme “en” derives verb word. The noun “threat” is a statement of an intention to inflict pain, injury, damage, or other hostile action on someone in retribution for something done or not done” added with a suffix “en” derives a new word “threaten”. A verb that stated to give signs or warning. This is the sample statement that unveiled this derivational process in the corpora.

“This ceasefire agreement should be unconditional as it benefit both parties to the conflict and help the threaten citizens” (SK-06)

Moreover, another derivational morpheme that found in the gathered corpora. The word with lexical category of a noun attached by morpheme or suffix it derives verb word. The word “strength” is a noun which means “power to resist force” when added with a suffix “en” it creates a new word and it became “strengthen”. A verb that means “to make stronger”. Therefore, this show on how the root words changed in lexical category through attachment of derivational morpheme. This is the sample statement that revealed this derivational process in the corpora.

“May his memory light up the fire within us and strengthen ourselves to become patriots” (SK-08)

Inflectional morpheme. Inflectional morphemes change the form of a word but not its lexical category or its central meaning. This kind of morphemes create variant forms of a word to conform to different roles in a sentence or discourse. In this study, affixes that was added to a word (a noun, verb, adjective or an adverb) to assign a particular grammatical property to that word, such as its tense, number, possession, or comparison. Unlike derivational morpheme that can be a suffix or a prefix, inflectional morpheme only added

at the end of a word or suffix. The examples of inflectional morphemes in English were the bound morphemes –s or es, ‘s or s’, ed, en, er, and ing. These suffixes used to tell a certain aspect of the root word.

As shown in Table 1.1.2 below, the study found the complete presentation of words in Sangguniang Kabataan which undergo an inflectional process as morphological aspect. The sample statements or the corpora where the inflectional process have been found were also included. The bold group of letters or the suffix in the sample statement indicates that the word undergone inflectional process.

As stipulated in the tabular presentation below, the use of inflectional morpheme was evident in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns. The morpheme, s and es when attached to a noun might indicate numbers or possession. The word “talent” when added with a morpheme “s” resulting to a new meaning stated that it is refers to multiple instances of individual abilities or skills possessed by different people.

Table 1.1.2. *Inflectional Morpheme*

<i>Inflectional morpheme</i>	<i>Function</i>	<i>Sample statements</i>
-s, -es	Indicate numbers	“I hope we will have opportunity to do this work in order to develop the talents and skills of our youth” SK-01 “We should be open-minded to explore our ability or skills, because this is a step towards success” SK-04 “We are aware that there are many of lesbians and gays here in barangay poblacion if we have a chance to sit for this upcoming election” SK-05 “The mission that being promote for the abilities and awareness of the youth and to protect the environment, as well as to prepare for times of calamity” SK-03
-ed	indicate tense	“I am standing in front of you, not money I used to be run, I don’t have money but I have platforms” SK-06 “I’m here, standing in front, and requesting to all of you to give me a chance to handle this big responsibility that I wanted to” SK-07 “I run as SK chairman and I know what I entered for, and I know being SK chairman is not anyone simply to enter and this is not just merely position to fill”. SK-09 “I just want to help the students here in barangay Bacasi so that they can be motivated to continue their studies despite whatever difficulties they may face” SK-10
-er and -est	Indicate degree	“Barangay Población will be even better, livelier, and more beautiful in a good way with us serving the people here” SK-05 “I want to include also the taekwondo because it was the highest rating in Davao Del Norte and it can help also for self-defense in every person” SK-06 “Let’s join for the improvement in order to have safest and future prosper in our community” SK-03

“I hope we will have more opportunity to do some work in order to develop the talents and skills of our youth” (SK-01)

Another, inflectional morpheme found in the gathered corpora, the word “skill” is the base form and when it is added with a morpheme “s” it became “skills”. Therefore, the derived meaning is encompassing a broader spectrum of abilities or proficiencies. Below were the sample statements that were found in the analyzed corpora.

“We should be open-minded to explore our ability or skills, because this is a step towards success” (SK-04)

Another, inflectional morpheme found in the gathered corpora, the word “skill” is the base form and when it is added with a morpheme “s” it became “skills”. Therefore, the derived meaning is encompassing a broader spectrum of abilities or proficiencies. Below were the sample statements that were found in the analyzed corpora.

“We should be open-minded to explore our ability or skills, because this is a step towards success” (SK-04)

Furthermore, the words "lesbian" and "gay" change when the morpheme "-s" is added, becoming "lesbians" and "gays," which shifts the focus from the individual to a broader group. Similarly, the word "time" undergoes a shift in meaning when the plural morpheme "-s" is added, broadening its scope from a singular instance to encompass multiple instances or periods. This shift in meaning allows it also to encompass more circumstances or skills or competencies. Here’s the complete statement in the following;

“We are aware that there are many of lesbians and gays here in barangay Poblacion if we have a chance to sit for this upcoming election” (SK-05)

“The mission that being promote for the ability’s awareness of the youth and to protect the environment, as well as to prepare for times of calamity” (SK-03)

On the other hand, words with a lexical category of verb, attachment of a morpheme like “ed” can mark such categories as tense or number. This morpheme when added to a verb signify a new class of a verb which constituted a past tense. The word “enter” is a verb which means to come or go attached a morpheme “ed” creates a new grammatical category “entered” and mark it as past tense category.

“I run as SK chairman and I know what I entered for, and I know being SK chairman is not anyone simply to enter and this is not just merely position” (SK-09)

Moreover, the word “want” in the statement is a verb, it means to have a desire to possess or do along, however, when added by with a suffix “ed” and it becomes “wanted”. Therefore, this morpheme when added to a verb it thus shows a new grammatical category of a verb which is made of a past tense. Below were the sample statements that was analyzed in the gathered corpora:

“I’m here, standing in front, and requesting to all of you to give me a chance to handle this big responsibility that I wanted to” (SK-07)

Aside from that, the word “motivate” it is also a verb that means wishing for something to happen, but when added by with a suffix “d” it became “motivated” and it change to the past tense category. Also, the verb “use” attached with a suffix “ed” it became “used” and it change to past tense category. Therefore, this morpheme when attached to a verb it indicates a new grammatical category of a verb that formed of a past tense. Shown below are the sample statements that was analyzed in the gathered corpora:

“I am standing in front of you, not money I used to be run, I don’t have money but I have platforms” (SK-06)

Aside from that, the word “Motivation” is a verb and its meaning refers to encouraging someone or stimulating him or her to get something/ do something. The suffix “d” changes the noun to the past tense, making the word “motivated” which tells us the action has already taken place. Here’s the complete statement below;

“I just want to help the students here in barangay Bacasi so that they can be motivated to continue their studies despite whatever difficulties they may face” (SK-10)

Nonetheless, morpheme like “er” and “est” when attached to an adjective it indicates degree. The suffix “est” when attached to an adjective indicates a superlative degree of a word. The word “highest” is an adjective in superlative degree that means it implies reaching the peak of accomplishment. The word “safest” also belong to adjective in superlative category which means refers to the most secure. The statement below shows the utilization of this morphological process in the corpora.

“I want to include also the taekwondo because it was the highest rating in Davao Del Norte and it can help also for self-defense in every person” (SK-06)

“Let’s join for the improvement in order to have safest and future prosper in our community” (SK-03)

On the other hand, the analyzed gathered corpora was utilized on the Sangguniang Kabataan uses a comparative degree of a word. The word “live” is an adjective and were added by a suffix “er” it became “livelier” as comparative word. Therefore, the word has a change happened. Therefore, below shows the utilization of this morphological process in the gathered corpora.

“Barangay Población will be even better, livelier, and more beautiful in a good way with us serving the people here” (SK-05)

Compounding. In addition to the morphological analysis, compounding entails the formation of the forms from smaller parts of several words and as such the form usually has the meaning entirely distinct from the individual words used in their formation. Such components can be referred to any lexical category and do not have to belong to a single category in particular. In the context to the words present in Sangguniang Kabataan during speech election campaigns, different words were combined, and which produced another word with distinct meaning.

In addition, compound words do not act as according to the number of words being combined but as individual word with one meaning. In other words, it is the process of combining two or more distinct words and make it work together. Most of the parts of speech can be utilized to form a compound word. Nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and even prepositions might be used as components of a compound words. Compound words were somehow confused as blended words but in compounding, the words being compound does not change in structure, blended word does.

As presented in Table 1.1.3, the study uncovered that Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns contained compound words or undergo the process of compounding as part of the morphological aspect. The table also included the sample words and the individual words that being combined. The meaning of each word and the new meaning of the derive word. The sample statement from the corpora was also presented.

As presented in the table below, compound words are evident in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns. These are particularly dominant in the corpora being gathered. The compound word “scholarship”, which is a combination of the word “scholar” and “ship”, was found present in Sangguniang Kabataan, which means award of financial aid for a student to further their education. The sentence below shown how the compounded word was utilized in the analyzed corpora.

“As a voice assistant manager for the past few months, I am one who accepted the scholarship assistance, who is the one encoded and accompanied” (SK-06)

“The sk council will lead the santolan reintegration program for out of school youth, scholarship for Santolan’s students” (SK-02)

Apart from that, the word “earthquakes” which is formed by the two words “earth” and “quakes” was also a compounded word which

means are the result of sudden movements in the earth’s crust, causing the ground to shake. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used term in the following statement:

“This is aimed at providing knowledge to our youth on what do in case of natural calamities such as floods, fires, and earthquakes” (SK-07)

Table 1.1.3. *Compounding in Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns*

Term	Structure	Sample statement
Scholarship	Scholar (n)- refers to someone who engages in academic study or research, often at a higher educational institution. ship (n) – large seagoing vessel Scholar + ship = Scholarship Scholarship is an award of financial aid for a student to further their education.	“As a voice assistant manager for the past few months, I am one who accepted the scholarship assistance, who is the one encoded and accompanied” SK-06 “The sk council will lead the santolan reintegration program for out of school youth, scholarship for santolan students” SK-02
Earthquakes	Earth (n)- is the planet only known celestial body to support life. Quakes (v)-refers to sudden and violent shaking of the ground caused by the movement. Earth + quakes = Earthquakes Earthquakes- are the result of sudden movements in the earth’s crust, causing the ground to shake	“This is aimed at providing knowledge to our youth on what do in case of natural calamities such as floods, fires, and earthquakes.” SK-07
Teenage	teen (n)- is the particular person’s age from 13 to 19 years old age (n)-the length of the time of the person has lived or a thing has existed teen + age = teenage teenage- refers to the period of an individual’s life.	“One of the other programs is all about the reproductive health and safe choices for bright future: SK contraceptive awareness campaign against the teenage pregnancy” SK-08
Upcoming	Up (adv)- one in a high or advantageous position. Coming (adj)- due to happen or successful in the future Up+ coming= Upcoming Upcoming – refers to something that is about to happen or is coming soon in the near future.	“If we have a chance to sit for this upcoming election, we will make sure that not only the sports are inclusive for boys and girls, but we will also prioritize the third platform for LGBTQ+.” SK-05
disabilities	dis (n) – speak disrespectfully to or criticize abilities (n)- possession of the means or skill to do something. dis + abilities = disabilities disabilities- a physical or mental condition that limits a person’s movements, senses, or activities	“The PWDs specially those children with disabilities where we can provide medical assistance for them” SK-08

In addition, the compound word “teenage” which is a combination of the noun word “teen” and “age” that is a noun was found present in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns which means refers to the period of an individual’s life. The sentences below shown how the compounded word was utilized in the analyzed corpora.

“One of the other programs is all about the reproductive health and safe choices for bright future: SK contraceptive awareness campaign against the teenage pregnancy” (SK-08)

Besides, the word “upcoming” which created from the two different words “up” which is an adverb a one in a high or advantageous position and “coming” which is also an adjective which means due to happen or successful in the future. The two different words combine into “upcoming” means is refers to something that is about to happen or is coming soon in the near future. Here’s sample statement below.

“If we have a chance to sit for this upcoming election, we will make sure, that not only the sports are inclusive for boys and girls, but we will also prioritize the third platform for LGBTQ+” (SK-05)

Also, with the word “disabilities” which created different meanings “dis” which is verb, which means speak disrespectfully to or criticize and the word “abilities” which is a noun, means a possession of the means or skill to do something. Sample statement from Sangguniang Kabataan follows:

“The PWDs specially those children with disabilities where we can provide medical assistance for them” (SK-08)

Compounding plays an important role in discourses and public speaking as it allows speakers to create new words by combining two or more existing words, which can help in conveying complex ideas more effectively. In public speaking, the use of compound words can make the speech more engaging and memorable for the audience. Additionally, compound words can be used to create catchy and memorable phrases, which can help to reinforce key points in the speech.

Therefore, from the above-mentioned corpora revealed the utilization of compounding in Sangguniang Kabataan. Compounding is one of the ways to catch the attention of the listeners specifically the voters. They can be used to convey complex ideas in a concise manner and can help to make the speech more engaging and memorable. In public speaking, specifically the speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan, the use of compound words can help to create a sense of rhythm and flow, making it easier for your audience to follow along with your message. Overall, compounding enhances the expressiveness and effectiveness of language, making it a valuable tool for public speakers and discourse participants.

Initialisms. Initialisms are morphological processes that create shortenings like acronyms, but pronounced as sequences of letters. They are created by compounding the initial letters of a set of words to form one form. Initialisms are crucial in language evolution, reflecting the dynamic nature of language and its adaptability to changing needs. They provide a convenient way to refer to new concepts, technologies, and organizations without needing to create new words. Initialisms play a significant role in political speech by considering complex concepts or organizations into easily recognizable shorthand. By demonstrating expertise, passion, and enthusiasm, initialism helps speakers gain the trust and respect of their audience, making them more receptive to the presentation's message.

As displayed in Table 1.1.4 below, the study found in the Sangguniang Kabataan utilized initialisms as morphological aspect in presenting their ideas and messages. The table shown the initialization and its individual meaning. Shown also in the table was the structure and the denotative meaning of the initialized letters as according of which it refers and usage. The sample statements from the Sangguniang Kabataan as the corpora where the initialisms found, were also presented.

Furthermore, initialisms have become pervasive in modern communication, particularly in fields characterized by specialized vocabulary and complex terminology. Initialisms can serve as powerful tools for persuasion, branding, and simplifying messaging and can be used strategically to frame issues or shape public perception, depending on how they are employed within political rhetoric. As presented on Table 1.1.4, four terms were founded present in Sangguniang Kabataan. These are “HIV”, “NGO”, “LGBTQ+”, “STD”, “BFP” and “DRRR”.

Table 1.1.4. *Initialisms in Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns*

Term	Structure	Sample statement
HIV	H+I+V H- Human I-Immunodeficiency V-Virus	“Awareness program breaking the stigma about the HIV” SK-08
NGO	N+G+O N-Non G-Government O-Organization	“Partnership with NGOs along with this program” SK-08
LGBTQ+	L+G+B+T+Q L- Lesbian G-Gay B-Bisexual T- Transgender Q-Queer	“If we have a chance to sit for this upcoming election, we will make sure that not only the sports are inclusive for boys and girls, but we will also prioritize the third platform for LGBTQ+” SK-05
STD	S+T+D S-Sexually T- Transmitted	“Youth voices matter: promoting inclusivity in reproductive health together with by launching of STD awareness program breaking the stigma about the HIV/AIDS” SK-08
DRR	D+R+R+R D-Disaster R-Risk R-Reduction	“DRR, it includes in order to plan the important for the nature and the safety, this is the mission that being promote for the abilities and awareness of the youth and to protect the environment, as well as to prepare for times of calamity” SK-03

In connection, the initialism “HIV” or Human immunodeficiency virus this refer to a virus that attacks the body’s immune system and this condition where the immune system becomes severely weakened, making the person vulnerable to opportunistic infections and cancers. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this initialisms “HIV” during their speech to quicker remember and more convenient terminology to specify private interactions. Here’s the complete statement in the following:

“Awareness program breaking the stigma about the HIV” (SK-08)

On the other hand, another initialism founded in Sangguniang Kabataan is “NGO” which stands for non- government organization. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the term “NGO” was used to highlight the involvement and partnership of non-governmental organization program emphasize with the collaborative effort, the speaker was used this initialisms “NGO” to understand and remember easily when hearing this term, the audience may find convenient and quick to remember. Here’s the sentence complete below.

“Partnership with NGOs along with this Program” (SK-08)

On the other hand, another initialism founded in Sangguniang Kabataan is “NGO” which stands for non- government organization. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the term “NGO” was used to highlight the involvement and partnership of non-governmental organization program emphasize with the collaborative effort, the speaker was used this initialisms “NGO” to understand and remember easily when hearing this term, the audience may find convenient and quick to remember. Here’s the sentence complete below.

“Partnership with NGOs along with this Program” (SK-08)

Moreover, the “LGBTQ+” which stands for Lesbian Gay Bisexual Transgender Queer. LGBTQ+ this refers representing diverse sexual orientations and gender identities. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this term to acknowledge this group as a distinct category deserving of inclusion and support in sports activities with boys and girls also, this initialism “LGBTQ” may the audience and speaker find convenient and equal respect from each other. As taken from corpora, it was being utilized in the sample statement below.

“If we have a chance to sit for this upcoming election, we will make sure that not only the sports are inclusive for boys and girls, but we will also prioritize the third platform for LGBTQ+” (SK-05)

In addition, another initialism founded in Sangguniang Kabataan is the “STD” stands for sexually transmitted disease which means is an infection that are typically transmitted through sexual contact, including vaginal, anal, or oral sex. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this initialisms “STD” to make easily to remember and understand by the audience. Here’s the sample statement below.

“Youth voices matter: promoting inclusivity in reproductive health together with by launching of STD awareness program breaking the stigma about the HIV/AIDS” (SK-08)

Furthermore, the initialisms “DRR” stands for disaster risk reduction which means is the ability of individuals and recover from impacts of hazards in a timely and efficient manner. In the context of Sangguniang they use this initialisms “DRR” to easily remember by the audience, may the audience can find convenient and comfortable when hearing the words through using initialisms and it leaves long lasts in their minds. The sample statement taken from the corpora was stated below.

“DRR, it includes in order to plan the important for the nature and the safety, this is the mission that being promote for the abilities and awareness of the youth and to protect the environment, as well as to prepare for times of calamity” (SK-03)

Semantic Features in Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns

Semantics is the branch of linguistics concerned with the meaning of words, phrases, sentences, and larger chunks of discourse. It explores how language conveys meaning through the relationships between words and their referents in the world, as well as the relationships between different parts of a sentence or text.

The fundamental function of every language system is to link meaning and expression. Semantic functions provide the necessary context and underlying meaning to interpret figurative language effectively, helping readers and listeners understand the intended metaphorical or non-literal expressions.

The words/phrases in Table 1.2 are terms commonly find in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns. Thus, these are analyzed based on dictionary meaning and its referential meaning. The dictionary meaning of a word or phrase represents its general definition, while referential meaning in this context pertains specifically to how that word or phrase is used and understood within election campaigns setting.

The specialized referential meaning often emerges from the unique circumstances and objectives of Sangguniang Kabataan speeches. The interaction between these dictionary meanings and their context- specific referential counterparts is pivotal, as it directly influences how voters or audiences perceive, engage with, and make decisions regarding how politicians convey their speeches.

In this research materials gathered, a recurring pattern emerges, revealing the prevalence of certain words or terms. These words and terms are consistently employed throughout the data, suggesting their significance in the context of the study. The frequent appearance underscores their role as central elements within the research materials. Shown are the terms that were commonly found in the gathered corpora.

In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan, the word “sana all” in English “I hope everyone, or I wish everyone” it takes on unique role. When the candidate or audience use this term, they are essentially expressing their desire to achieved or to hope also this often used to express a desire for inclusivity or it used to convey the candidate’s promise of equal opportunity and benefits for all citizen, by implying this term it aims to uplift everyone. The word “Sana all” was manifested in the following statement:

“More sana all. Yes, to team UNLAD you will sure” (SK-01)

Furthermore, in the statement below is another semantic word was found in the gathered corpora. The word “Werpa” it often used as a slang term In English translation “Power”, during election campaigns it can used to energize supporters or to describe a candidate’s strength and influence. Candidates or supporters may shout “werpa” in rallies to express support and enthusiasm. The term “Werpa”

was manifested in the following statement:

Table 1.2. *Semantic features in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns*

<i>Semantic</i>	<i>Sample Statements</i>	<i>Dictionary Meaning</i>	<i>Referential Meaning</i>
Sana all	“More sana all. Yes, to team UNLAD you will sure” SK-01	It is an expression used to wish or hope for an individual accomplishment or success.	Refers to a statement made by speaker or audience during an actual election campaign or express that everybody could be more hopeful when they vote the team.
Werpa	“Vote team suluguon kay naa na ang werpa na ready mo tabang sa mga Kabataan” SK-03	It is used to express support or motivation, especially on the particular context.	Refers to a statement made by speaker or the speaker would use this term as to convince the audience, this term in English grammar is “power”.
Lodi	“Ako diay si Ramon Chatto Jr. ang lodi sa team suluguon” SK-05	It refers when you admire someone as you would an idol.	This term was used by the speaker during election campaign in order to gain admiration, emphasizing the positive lights and popularity.
Petmalu	“Hinding hindi kami susuko dahil kami ay petmalu’ng malupet na handing magserbisyo” SK-06	It describes to a someone they admire and see as worthy of praise.	This term it refers to attempt to connect with the voters or it refers something that is extraordinarily good, cool, and stand out remarkable way.
Piece of cake	“Entering this political environment is not a piece of cake like what we think, it is a kind of huge responsibilities” SK-05	This refers to something that is very easy to do or easily to achieved.	This term does not have literal meaning but it refers to something that easy to achieved
Mekus-mekus	“Ayaw Ninyo e-mekus mekus ang inyong huna-huna, kundi botohi Ninyo ang tinud anay na mo serbisyo” SK-01	It is used to describe the action of mixing something particularly mixing ingredients in the context of food preparation.	This term is to tell people that should be vote only those who are they think qualified and enough to be leader without doubt and hesitation.
Once in a blue moon	“I don’t want happened again here in our barangay, some political candidate before, show only once in a blue moon, only election campaigns” SK-10	This refers to do it very rarely.	This phrase refers to the particular event or promise is so rare that its almost unlikely to happen again. For instance, a political emphasize how infrequent and significant their achievement or promises are.
Barkada	“Let us treat ourselves na mag barkada, dapat magtinabangay kita aron sa paglambo sa akong barangay” SK-03	It refers to the group of people also known as a close friend	This term to describe people who share strong bond or close associates who support a particular candidate or cause.
Mine	“Wag ninyong kalimutan ang aming grupo e-mine Ninyo kami” SK-04	Used to refer to a thing belonging to or associated with the speaker.	Refers to a statement made by speaker or participant during an election campaign as to claim or to vote them certainly.
Steal	“We need to helping each other, no need to steal someone’s rights to vote in order for you to win” SK-10	To take another person’s property without permission or by force.	Used to convey a sense of injustice or illegitimacy or they believe the opponent is engaging in dishonest practices to win.

“Vote team suluguon kay naa na ang werpa na ready mo tabang sa mga Kabataan” (SK-03)

(Vote for Team Suluguon because the power is ready to help the youth)

In addition, the word “Lodi” is the Filipino slang for “idol” used to describe someone admired or respected, the candidates use this term to appeal to younger voters by presenting themselves as role models or figures to look up. Also, using this term it can be part of a strategy to engage gain support or favor among their target audience. The word “Lodi” was manifested in the following statement:

“Ako diay si Ramon Chatto Jr., ang lodi sa team suluguon” (SK-05)

(I am Ramon Chatto Jr., the idol of Team Suluguon)

Moreover, another sample statement was found in the gathered corpora. The word “Petmalu” is a Filipino slang derived from the word “Malupit”, which means “cool” or “awesome” in English, this term is the common strategy in political aspects to engage with the voters, also often used informally in various context to express admiration or praise.

“Hinding hindi kami susuko dahil kami ay petmalu’ng malupet na handing magserbisyo” (SK-06)

(We will not give up because we are incredibly tough and always ready to serve)

On the other hand, “Piece of cake” is an idiom that generally means something is very easy to accomplish. This phrase was used in election campaigns as to convey confidence about achieving victory, also it can lead backfire if it comes across as overconfidence. The phrase “Piece of cake” was manifested in the following statement:

“Entering this political environment is not a piece of cake like what we think, it is a kind of huge responsibilities” (SK-05)

Furthermore, in the statement below, effectively seen which the semantic was found in the gathered corpora. The “Mekus-Mekus” was the new Filipino slang word which derived from “Mix”, in the context of election campaign the candidate used this term to express and to tell that when the voters are going to vote must be choose the certain candidate and no more mixing any ideas and hesitation. The term “Mekus-Mekus” was found in the gathered corpora:

“Ayaw Ninyo e-mekus mekus ang inyong huna-huna, kundi botohi Ninyo ang tinud any na mo serbisyo” (SK-01)

(Do not let your mind be confused, instead vote for the one who will truly serve)

In addition, other statement below where the semantic was effectively found in the gathered corpora. The term “Once in a blue moon” does not have literal meaning in which is an idiomatic expression used to describe something that happens rarely. In context, a candidate used this term as to express something negative or positive towards the opponent, it refers that political candidate only show in the times of election campaigns after that they would never see from the community, also it emphasizes that a particular event or opportunity is very rare happened or come. This term was used also in the Sangguniang Kabataan in the following statement:

“I don’t want happened again here in our barangay, some political candidate before, show only once in a blue moon, only election campaigns” (SK-10)

On the other note, the term "barkada" often used to describe a peer group circle of friends that youth leaders aim to reach engagement, the word "barkada" “in the context of Sangguniang Kabataan it emphasizes that is not just about friendship but also about creating a group that works collectively for the betterment of the youth and the community, a key goal of the SK. The word " Barkada" was found in the following statement:

“Let us treat ourselves na mag barkada, dapat magtinabangay kita aron sa paglambo sa atong barangay” (SK-03)

(Let us treat ourselves as a group of friends; we should help each other in order to improve our barangay)

Moreover, the word "mine" is used as a possessive pronoun or possession of something by the speaker. But, in the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the word " mine" is uniquely used by the candidate or speaker, they used the word "mine" as to create personal connection towards the voters. The word "mine" was manifested in the gathered corpora in the following statement.

“Wag ninyong kalimutan ang aming grupo e-mine Ninyo kami” (SK-04)

(Don’t forget our group, mine us)

In addition, the word "steal" is often used to describe accusations or concerns about electoral fraud, manipulation, or unfair practices. For instance, candidate might claim that opponents are trying to "steal" the election by preventing certain groups from voting, tampering with ballots, or engaging in other forms of election. But, in the context of Sangguniang Kabataan during election campaign they used this term as to evoke strong emotions and to express the feelings towards the opponents, however it is meant to raise alarm and should be fair and allow voters to vote their own candidate. The word "steal" was manifested in the following statement.

“We need to helping each other, no need to steal someone’s rights to vote in order for you to win” (SK-10)

Syntactic Features of Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns

A clause is a set of words that makes up a sentence. It consists of a subject and a predicate. It can also be said that a clause should have a subject and a verb. A clause is a minimal grammatical unit that can contain a subject and a predicate. Clauses are the building blocks of sentences, and they can be either independent or dependent. A subject is the word that identifies the topic of a sentence or who is doing the activity and those were the words written in bold text. Therefore, the study is necessary find out the syntactic features of the speeches because the corpora utilize language.

The syntactic features of Sangguniang Kabataan are significant for several reasons. First, they play a crucial role in shaping the message and influencing the audience. The use of complex sentence structures, rhetorical devices, and a formal register can help to create a persuasive and convincing argument, and to convey a sense of authority and expertise. Second, syntactic features can help to create a sense of coherence and cohesion in the discourse, allowing politicians to express complex ideas and arguments in a clear and organized manner. Finally, syntactic features can help to create a sense of rhythm and flow in the discourse, making it more engaging and memorable for the audience.

Table 1.3. *Syntactic features of Sangguniang Kabataan in election campaigns*

<i>Types of Sentences</i>	<i>Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns</i>
Simple Sentence	“Let us show our love for our barangay” SK-01 “Ang pagselebrar sa piyesta maghatag og bag-ong mga oportunidad para sa partisipasyon sa kabatan-onan”. SK-02 “I will do my best” SK-06 “We will have seminars like mental health awareness, because here in our barangay the emotions are too” SK-07 “I believe that youth’s health is the key for their brighter future” SK-08

	“Gusto nako na Sangguniang Kabataan mag tinabangay” SK-09
	“Being Sk chairman is my top choices” SK-10
Compound Sentence	“I am what I was today and what I will be tomorrow” SK-01
	“Ang pagselebrar sa piyesta maghatag og bag-ong mga oportunidad para sa partisipasyon sa kabatan-onan and isa pa the education is the foundation for their brighter future” SK-02
	“Nature is significant but we failed to protect” SK-05
	“Ming dagan ko as Sk Chairman and Kabalo kung unsa ang akong gi sudlan” SK-09
	“We will provide a program that can help to the youth and to encourage them to continue their studies” SK-10
Complex Sentence	“The grievance of the youth will be acknowledged, because that is important and valid too” SK-02
	“I will establish a committee focused on youth’s activity, aiming to provide active participation and experiences for young people” SK-04
	“It is essential to be focused, because I do believe the youth’s health is the key for their brighter future” SK-08
	“When it’s election session, they act as if they are really good in the eyes of audiences” SK-09
Compound Complex Sentence	“We will make sure that sports are not just for men and women, but we also include the LGBTQ+ community, because we know what we can offer and we believe in equal opportunities for everyone” SK-05
	“I and my father will be helping each other, and he will run as barangay captain because it brings positive changes” SK-07
	“Despite of my busy schedule I do manage, because of some matters however, I still prepare for the election campaigns” SK-08

Therefore, Table 1.3 revealed that Sangguniang Kabataan presented syntactic features. The Sangguniang Kabataan as corpora commonly used simple, compound and complex sentences. To have a clear understanding, the first column presents the types of sentence clause structure. The second column had SK which stands for Sangguniang Kabataan followed by numbers stand as the code for each corpus. The last column is the Sangguniang Kabataan that contained and used each type of sentence clause structure to be easily understood.

Simple Sentence. One of the syntactic levels which is made of a single independent clause that can stand alone. This independent clause consists of a subject refers a noun or a noun phrase indicating the main idea and a predicate refers a verb or a verb phrase expressing the main action. Shown in the following statements are the simple sentences that were found in the corpora:

In the sentence “let us show our love for our barangay,” the subject is “us.” While the verb is “show.” Therefore, this sentence is simple because it consists of a single independent clause with a clear subject and verb. There are no dependent clauses in this sentence. It conveys a straightforward statement, making it a simple sentence in terms of its grammatical structure.

“Let us show our love for our barangay” (SK-01)

Aside from that, in the sentence below, the subject is “Ang pagselebrar sa piyesta” and the predicate is “bag-ong mga oportunidad para sa partisipasyon sa kabatan-onan”. Therefore, this sentence considered as simple sentence because it consists of single independent clause with a clear subject and predicate. There are no dependent clause structures in the sentence in which it conveys straightforward statement making it a simple sentence. Here’s the complete sentence in the following:

“Ang pagselebrar sa piyesta maghatag og bag-ong mga oportunidad para sa partisipasyon sa kabatan-onan” (SK-02)

(The celebration of festival will offer new opportunities for youth’s participation)

Another example found from the corpora, the subject is “I” while, the predicate is “will do my best.” Therefore, this sentence is simple because it consists of only a single independent clause with clear subject and predicate. Here’s the complete statement in the following:

“Himoon nako ang tanan” (SK-06)

(I will do my best)

Furthermore, the statement below is considered as simple sentence, because it consists of a single independent clause that can stand alone as a complete thought. The subject of the sentence is "We" and the predicate is "will have seminars". Since the sentence can convey a full and coherent idea on its own without depending on any other clauses, it considered as a simple sentence. Here’s the complete thought:

“We will have seminars like mental health awareness, because here in our barangay the emotions valid too” (SK-07)

Aside from that, the statement is another example of simple sentence which found in the gathered corpora. The subject is “I” the verb is “do” Since it contains only one independent clause and can stand alone and also it convey a complete thought in the statement; therefore, it qualifies as a simple sentence in English grammar. Here’s statement below.

“I do believe that youth’s health is the key for their brighter future” (SK-08)

In addition, the subject is “Nako” the verb is “want” in the sentence, "gusto" is the main verb, and "Sangguniang Kabataan mag tinabangay" is the object complement, expressing what the speaker wants, and it only consists of one independent clause and can stand

alone as always. Here's the sample statement below.

“Gusto nako na Sangguniang Kabataan mag tinabangay” (SK-09)

(I want Sangguniang Kabataan to help each other)

Moreover, another simple sentence below the subject is "Being Sk chairman", while the verb "is" or the predicate in the sentence is “is my top choices” upon evaluating the sentence, it meets effectively the criteria for a simple sentence in English grammar because it only consists one independent clause and can stand alone. Here's the complete sentence.

“Being Sk chairman is my top choices” (SK-10)

Compound Sentence. Another component of the syntactic level is the compound sentence. A compound sentence is a sentence that has at least two or more independent clauses typically with a coordinating comma, semicolon and conjunctions such as for, and, not, but, or, yet, like, and so, are used to join these clauses together. Presented in the following are the compound sentences found in the materials gathered:

Below is the sample statement of the compound sentence it consists of two independent clauses. The first independent clause is “I am what I was today “then, second independent clause is “what I will be tomorrow” these two independent clauses joined together by conjunction “and”. Therefore, when combining the two clauses it creates compound.

“I am what I was today and what I will be tomorrow” (SK-01)

The statement below is the compound sentence found in Sangguniang Kabataan, because it consists of two independent clauses joined together by conjunction “and”. The first independent clause is “Ang pagselebrar sa piyesta maghatag og bag-ong mga oportunidad para sa partisipasyon sa kabatan-onan”. The second independent clause is “the education is the foundation for their brighter future”. When combining the two independent clauses it creates compound sentence.

“Ang pagselebrar sa piyesta maghatag og bag-ong mga oportunidad para sa partisipasyon sa kabatan-onan and the education is the foundation for their brighter future” (SK-02)

(The celebration of festival will offer new opportunities for youth's participation and the education is the foundation for their brighter future)

Another compound sentence found in Sangguniang Kabataan. The first independent clause is "Nature is significant," is an independent clause. The second independent clause is "we failed to protect" is another independent clause. These two independent clauses are joined by the coordinating conjunction "but" and making it a compound sentence. This structure allows the sentence to convey two related ideas in a single sentence.

“Nature is significant, but we failed to protect” (SK-05)

In addition, “Ming dagan ko as SK chairman" this is the first independent clause. While " Kabalo ko kung ang akong gi sudlan" this is the second independent clause. The two independent clauses are joined by the coordinating conjunction of "and," which resulted of compound sentence. The complete statement is below.

“Ming dagan ko as Sk Chairman and Kabalo kung unsa ang akong gi sudlan” (SK-09)

(I run as SK chairman, and I know what I entered for)

Lastly, another sample of compound sentence. First is “We will provide a program that can help to the youth” and this is an independent clause since it can stand alone. While “encourage them to continue their studies” is another independent clause because it can stand alone also. These two independent clauses are joined by the conjunction of “and”. Therefore, it is considered as compound sentence. Here's the complete statement below.

“We will provide a program that can help to the youth and to encourage them to continue their studies” (SK-10)

Complex Sentence. Complex sentence has one independent clause and one or more dependent clauses. This refers that independent clause has a subject and a verb and may be read as a complete sentence, both independent and dependent clauses are linked by subordinating conjunction. In case the subordinating conjunction seen in the beginning of a sentence forming a dependent clause, use a comma after it. When using a relative clause, should be enclosed within commas. The complex sentences were manifested in the gathered corpora from Sangguniang Kabataan.

The independent Clause " The grievance of the youth will be acknowledged" this part of the sentence can stand alone and expresses a complete thought. While the dependent Clause " that is important and valid too" this part of the sentence also it cannot stand alone because it depends on the independent clause for context. Then, it starts with the subordinating conjunction of "Because," indicating a connection both clauses. Therefore, when combining these two clauses, the sentences become complex because it contains both an independent clause and a dependent clause. The complete statement is below.

“The grievance of the youth will be acknowledged, because that is important and valid too” (SK-02)

Furthermore, the independent clause in the statement " I will establish a committee focused on youth's activity " and the dependent clause " aiming to provide active participation and experiences for young people " this statement it cannot stand alone as a complete sentence, because it depends on the independent clause. Therefore, when combining these two clauses together, it will create a complex sentence.

“I will establish a committee focused on youth's activity, aiming to provide active participation and experiences for young people” (SK-04)

Moreover, the statement below is the complex sentence which also found in Sangguniang Kabataan. The independent clause " It is essential to be focused " while the dependent clause: " because I do believe the youth's health is the key for their brighter future " this clause begins with the subordinating conjunction "because" and provides additional information about the main clause. The combination of these two clauses contributing different aspects which creates a complex sentence.

“It is essential to be focused, because I do believe the youth's health is the key for their brighter future” (SK-08)

Lastly, the statement of " They act as if they are really good in the eyes of audiences" is the independent clause because it can stand alone. While the statement of “even though their past actions suggest otherwise " this is dependent clause because it cannot stand its own. These two clauses were joined with coordinating conjunction of “even though”. Therefore, upon analyzing the statement given it have shown the qualification of complex sentence. Here's the sample statement below.

“They act as if they are really good in the eyes of audiences, even though their past actions suggest otherwise” (SK-09)

Compound-Complex Sentence. Is another syntactic level, compound-complex sentences are formed by combining compound and complex sentences. Also, this sentence consists of two or more independent clauses and at least one dependent clause. Similarly, compound sentence which consists of one or more dependent clauses, that are joined by a conjunction. These are long sentences that communicate a significant amount of information. Presented below are the compound-complex sentences found in the corpora gathered.

In the sentence, the first independent clause is “We will make sure that sports are not just for men and women”. The second independent clause is “but we also include the LGBTQ+ community” and the third independent clause is “we believe in equal opportunities for everyone” these three clauses can stand alone. However, the first and second independent clauses are joined with coordination conjunction of “but”. On the other hand, the dependent clause is “because we know what we can offer” this clause considered as cannot stand alone. Also, it coordinates with conjunction of “because”. Therefore, by combining these three clauses it certainly qualifies the compound-complex sentence. Here's the sample statement below.

“We will make sure that sports are not just for men and women, but we also include the LGBTQ+ community, because we know what we can offer and we believe in equal opportunities for everyone” (SK-05)

Moreover, in the sentence "I and my father will be helping each other" and "He will run for our barangay as captain" these two clauses are independent clause and can stand its own. It connected by coordinating conjunction of “and”. On the other hand, the sentence is " because it brings positive changes " this is a dependent clause obviously cannot stand by its own, also coordinating conjunction of “because” Therefore, it's a compound-complex sentence there is two independent and one dependent clause. Here's the complete statement.

“I and my father will be helping each other, and he will run as barangay captain because it brings positive changes” (SK-07)

Lastly, the first independent clause " I still manage to prepare for the election campaigns " and the second independent clause is “I make sure to address all important matters” These two clauses can stand alone as a complete sentence with coordinating conjunction of “and”. On the other hand, the dependent clause is “Although I have busy schedule” this refer it cannot stand alone and obviously started with coordinating conjunction of “Although”. Therefore, combining these sentences, it becomes compound-complex because it contains at least two independent clauses and one dependent clause.

“Although I have busy schedule, I still manage to prepare for the election campaigns, and I make sure to address all important matters” (SK-08)

Research Question 2: What are the rhetorical persuasion strategies present in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns?

In this part, it delved into the rhetorical strategies utilized by Sangguniang Kabataan election during campaigns. The analysis is based upon Lamb's theory (2019) in which he emphasizes that there are 25 features of persuasive techniques, those are alliteration, analogy, anecdote, appeals, assonance, attacks, cliché, connotation, emotive language, everyday/colloquial language, euphemism, evidence, hyperbole, generalization, expert opinion, inclusive language, imagery, jargon, logic/reason, metaphor, pun, repetition, rhetorical question, sarcasm, and simile. Table 2 probes the persuasive strategies present in Sangguniang Kabataan. Notably, techniques such as alliteration, analogy, anecdote, appeals, assonance, attacks, emotive language, everyday/colloquial language, euphemism, evidence, hyperbole, generalization, expert opinion, inclusive language, imagery, jargon, logic/reason, pun, repetition, rhetorical question, and simile were found. These techniques align with the context of Sangguniang Kabataan during election campaigns, where the candidate

aim to engage and convince their audience/voters in real time.

Table 2. *Persuasive Strategies employed in Sangguniang Kabataan Election Campaigns*

<i>Rhetorical Strategies</i>	<i>Sample Statement</i>
Repetition	<p>“It was really quiet before, very quiet! It's true, it was quiet! Where's the budget? That's true, not a joke” SK-01</p> <p>“If you vote, listen to the shout from your heart, not the tinkle of (money), you know! You know what I mean” SK-02</p> <p>“We really want to level up more in order the youth will do what they want as we wanted to do also” SK-05</p> <p>“I don't have money, but I have platform” SK-06</p> <p>“Because the success of the youth is the success of our barangay also” SK-07</p>
Inclusive Words	<p>“We are running for the youth” SK-01</p> <p>“Because we know there are many LGBTQ+ individuals in Barangay Población, and we are the ones who can serve in the upcoming election” SK-05</p> <p>I hope you will vote me SK-06</p> <p>“Parents, guardians, and all caregivers out there, please take care of your children” SK-09</p> <p>“Requesting your support for team SERBISYONG TOTOO” SK-10</p>
Emotive Words	<p>I'm very happy tungod kay anaa ang inyohang presensya SK-03</p> <p>We're not just all words, but we'll also act on this. Thank you for listening, and don't forget to vote us SK-05</p> <p>It so sad to say some people here are easily to buy tungod sa kwarta SK-08</p> <p>“I am confident standing in front of you without any nervous because kay kabalo ko sa akong sarili” SK-09</p> <p>“I just want to help the students here in barangay Bacasi so that they can be motivated to continue their studies despite whatever difficulties they may face” SK-10</p>
Generalization	<p>“Vote for the youth!” (SK-01)</p> <p>“Overall platforms for addressing environmental and climate disasters will be the “Natural Mind Academy”, consisting of seminars and workshops. Through collaboration with environmental organizations, NGOs, and university organizations, valuable information will be shared to aid in our efforts” (SK-03)</p> <p>“We should be open-minded to explore our ability or skills, because this is a step towards success” SK-04</p> <p>“Don't forget us, the team (SULUGUON) and team Buagas” SK-05</p> <p>“Vote for the youth!” SK-09</p> <p>“It's up to us! Vote that makes our barangay will be in a goods hand” SK-10</p>
Alliteration	<p>“Reduce, Reuse and Recycle Tree Planting Activity” SK-03</p> <p>“I want our barangay like the vegetables have go, glow and grow” SK-05</p> <p>“SKES (Sangguniang Kabataan Educational Support) is for high school, senior high, and college students who are striving to achieve their dreams” SK-07</p> <p>“I became part of senior supreme student council” SK-09</p>
Connotation	<p>“Our barangay is our second home. It is important to preserves the cleanliness and securities” SK-01</p> <p>“I feel the color today, you know why? Because I already see the Glimpse of lights here in our barangay” SK-03</p> <p>“My confidence brought me here to stand on the stage” SK-05</p> <p>“Let's spread love because it is so ugly that the community of barangay can't find peace like before” SK-07</p>
Rhetoric Questions	<p>“Because I know the issues here in the community, I am running for councilor. It was really quiet before, very quiet! It's true, it was quiet! Where's the budget?” SK-01</p> <p>“Where's the peace they promised before?” SK-03</p> <p>“This upcoming election, don't forget us?” SK-04</p> <p>“Hoping this upcoming election, you will vote the team Sulugon and the team Buagas. Are you willing to vote us?” SK-05</p> <p>“Are you willing to change your principles for just 300 pesos?” SK-06</p> <p>“Unsa may mahitabo sa council kung walay involvement sa kabatan-onan?” SK-10</p>
Anecdote	<p>“Gitudloan ko sa akong lolo, nga kaniadtong vice mayor pa siya diri sa New Corella, ang kahinungdanon sa tinuod nga pagserbisyo daw. Iyang ingon nga ang tinuod nga bahandi dili masukod sa kadako sa bank account, kundi sa pagkamaayo sa atong kasingkasing. Kinahanglan natong unahon ang kaayohan ug ang kaugmaon sa mga batan-on” SK-06</p> <p>“Sa dihang nagserbisyo ang akong amahan isip barangay captain, kanunay niyang ginasulti ang daghang responsibilidad nga dala sa maong papel. Usa ka istorya nga iyang gishare mao ang bahin sa usa ka kalihokan sa komunidad nga nahimong kalibog tungod sa kalit nga kusog nga ulan. Bisan pa sa kalibog, nagpabilin siyang kalmado, nagtukod ug nakig-coordinate sa mga boluntaryo aron ibalhin ang tanan sa sulod sa balay ug masiguro nga ang tanan luwas ug komportable. Ang iyang dedikasyon dili tungod sa pagpaningkamot nga makakuha ug kasikat o pagkilala; kini mahitungod sa tinuod nga pag-atiman sa mga tawo nga iyang ginaserbisyoan. Pinaagi sa mga hagit nga iyang naagian, gitudloan niya ako nga ang liderato mao ang pag-una sa uban ug ang pagpangita ug solusyon bisan pa sa labing lisud nga mga sitwasyon” SK-10</p>
Appeals	<p>“We are only running because we are commanded by the Almighty” SK-01</p> <p>“Your votes bring us good luck and fortune, especially in our barangay” SK-02</p> <p>“Violent Against Women and Children, this kind of case are dominant in our barangay. If I will win, I would like to implement a symposium at our school to aimed and empowering these victims to stand up for their rights” SK-06</p> <p>“I aim to prioritize inclusivity and equality in my platforms. My goal is to create opportunities for all youth to</p>

	participate in every event, not just those who good in sports, but also those who good in education games” SK-09 “I have noticed that many youths are dropping out of school because life is really hard, especially here. As a SK council we pray to God to allow us to provide programs that can help the youth, at least to provide for their basic needs and of course to encourage them to continue their studies” SK-10
Hyperbole	“Because I know the issues here in the community it was really quiet before, very quiet! It's true, it was quiet! Where's the budget? That's true, not a joke, but now we're running for the Youth” SK-01 “Youth there, I will tell you a million times. Vote with all your hearts” SK-03 “I have a lot of action than words” SK-05 “I am introvert person this opportunity is impossible” SK-06 “People here would sell out for a few cents!” SK-08
Colloquial Language	“More sana all. Yes, to team UNLAD you will sure” SK-01 “Good evening Mga Madi! Thank you for coming.” SK-02 “Vote team SULUGUON kay naa na ang werpa na ready mo tabang sa mga Kabataan” SK-03 “Ako diay si Ramon Chatto Jr. ang lodi sa team sulugon” SK-05 “Mga inday og dodong diha sa kilid kilid ayaw tawon ninyo kalimti mi sa umaabot na election” SK-06
Analogy	“You just have to vote with all your hearts why? Because someone says that life is like a box of chocolate. You never know what you're gonna get” SK-02 “Kabalo nata daan kung unsa ang mahitabo sa atong barangay, we have eyes and ears who witnessed sa tanan, our eyes are to seeing as ears are to hearing. Therefore, please vote wisely” SK-04 “Education is like a power, that we can use to change the world” SK-09 “Para sa umaabot na election kung unsa man ang resulta I can say that winning is a joy as losing is a defeat, I will remain to choose the acceptance, at least I try SK-10”
Simile	“Our barangay is like our home; we need to take care of it” SK-02 “Ang mga kabatan-onan mura'g adlaw nga nagdala ug kahayag sa komunidad” SK-04 “Ang kabatan-onan mao ang nagahimo sama sa kalambuan, sama sa mga bitoon nga nagagiya kanato sa dalan sa kalibog ug kawalay kasigurohan” SK-06 “Ang SK chairman sama sa ka lig-on nga kahoy nga nagabarug bisan sa tunga sa bagyo, kanunay nga gagiya ug suporta para sa iyang mga kauban” SK-09 “Sa kalisod nga atong panag-uban ming gaan sama sa suga nga nagabuhat sa atong dalan. Kusgan kaayo ta sama sa pader, nagtinabangay sa pag-atubang sa tanan natong mga hagit” SK-10
Imagery	“Because I know the issues here in the community, I am running for councilor. It was really quiet before, very quiet! It's true, it was quiet! Where's the budget? That's true, not a joke, but now we're running for the children. Will you vote for us?” SK-01 “I see the light of our barangay because of the youth here!” SK-02 “You know what we youth is like a sun who bring lights to the community” SK-04 “I already smell, that if you will vote team Sulugon you will never get disappoint by choosing us” SK-07 “Preserve the smile bright” SK-08 “Your vote will change the color of our barangay, what I mean is to change the future” SK-10
Assonance	“United we stand, hand in hand, to demand a brighter land” SK-02 “Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle Tree Planting Activity” SK-03 “Negosyo mo, paunlarin mo” SK-04 “I want our barangay like the vegetables have go, glow and grow” SK-05 “If I will win this is meant, if lose this is not defeat but this is fate” (SK-07)

Repetition. One persuasive strategy in Sangguniang Kabataan is repetition. As the name implies, it is the repetition of words or phrases to emphasize specific points that help listeners remember and understand the information presented to them. Moreover, it clarifies and reinforces key points that can draw the attention of the listeners to the information presented. It is also used strategically to create rhythm and flow which can create a sense of symmetry and balance. Repetition can occur at various levels, from individual words to entire sentences or paragraphs.

In the statement below, the word “quiet” is repeated which is refers to the state of calm or lack of activity in the community. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the repeating of the word, where the speaker emphasizes how noticeable this quietness before when the former candidates who led during their time, it shows that there is no active participation happened. However, the speaker aims to address through having significant change for their barangay. Here's the complete statement in the following:

It was really quiet before, very quiet! It's true, it was quiet! Where's the budget? That's true, not a joke (SK-01)

Moreover, the words “you know” is the repetition words that creates persuasion in the statement. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan, this repetition words it reinforces the idea of the listener to understands speaker's message, where making it more persuasive, because the candidate is trying to establish a connection, encourage, and create an intimacy towards the voters. The sample statement below was found in the Sangguniang Kabataan which used repetition.

“If you vote, listen to the shout from your heart, not the tinkle of (money), you know! You know what I mean” (SK-02)

Furthermore, the repetition word that creates a persuasive tone in the given statement is "want." It appears twice in the statement which

emphasizing the desire and determination behind the action. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the repetition of word it reinforces the idea that their desire is genuine and sincere, where the candidate is trying to innovate or change the styles before, in order to have meaningful and active participation of the youths. Therefore, it became persuasive to the audience because it appeals to their emotions and aligning with the speaker's intentions. Overall, the repetition of "want" adds emphasis to the statement, making it more persuasive in encouraging others to follow their lead. Here's the complete sentence below:

"We really want to level up more in order the youth will do what they want as we wanted to do also" (SK-05)

Furthermore, the repetition of the word "success." By repeating this word, the statement emphasizes the positive outcome and reinforces the idea that the prosperity of the youth directly contributes to the prosperity of the barangay. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan, the repetition of the word "success" helps to drive home to the point and persuade the audience of the importance of supporting and investing in the youth for the betterment of the community. Here's the complete statement below:

"Because the success of the youth is the success of our barangay also" (SK-07)

Inclusive words. Inclusive words refer to using words and phrases that avoid excluding particular groups of people based on factors such as race, gender, age, disability, sexual orientation, or socioeconomic status. It aims to promote diversity, equity, and respect for all individuals. Examples include using "they" as a singular pronoun, instead of assuming someone's gender, or using "chairperson" instead of "chairman" to avoid gender bias. Inclusive words are crucial during election campaigns because it shows respect for diverse groups of people, fosters a sense of belonging, and demonstrates a commitment to representing all constituents regardless of their background, beliefs, or identities. It helps candidates connect with a wider audience and build trust and support among various communities.

In connection, in the statement below, which used of inclusive words found in the Sangguniang Kabataan. The word "We" is an inclusive pronoun it refers to oneself and group of people. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used the term "We" to implies a sense of unity, and the speaker is already part of a larger group who also working towards a common goal of serving and supporting young people. Therefore, by using inclusive words like "we," candidates can effectively connect with the youth, through inspire them to get involved, and mobilize their support during election campaigns. The sample statement which gathered from Sangguniang Kabataan is in the following:

"We are running for the youth" (SK-01)

Moreover, another inclusive word found in Sangguniang Kabataan. The word "LGBTQ+" it refers to the diverse of sexual orientations and gender identities. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the term "LGBTQ" is considered as inclusive words because they are not referring one person but it refers to all individuals, this inclusivity shows a persuasive strategy because it acknowledges and respects the diversity within the community, by promoting acceptance and understanding for all individuals regardless of their sexual orientation or gender identity. The sample statement found in Sangguniang Kabataan is in the following:

"Because we know there are many LGBTQ+ individuals in Barangay Población, and we are the ones who can serve in the upcoming election" (SK-05)

Furthermore, another inclusive word found in the gathered corpora. The word "You" it's generally considered as inclusive word because it refers to the person being addressed, meaning whoever the speaker is talking to. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use the term "you" as to personally addressed and involved and it is considered as powerful persuasive tool because it directly engages to the audience or voters. Therefore, it is inclusive because it's addressing the listener directly. Here's the complete sample statement in the following:

"I hope you will vote me" (SK-06)

Moreover, another inclusive word was manifested in the gathered corpora. The word "caregivers" it is considered as inclusive word because it covers anyone who provides care, regardless of their relationship toward the children. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use the word "caregivers" to highlight everyone especially the parents, the speaker used this term as persuasive strategy by telling the parents to taking care of their children, when they heard the message, the audience will awake and see the truthfulness. Here's the complete sentence below.

"Parents, guardians, and all caregivers out there, please take care of your children" (SK-09)

Lastly, the word "team" refers to a group of people working together towards a common goal, regardless of individual differences such as gender, race, or background. It emphasizes collaboration and unity among its members. In the context of election campaigns, using "team" effectively can persuade voters by creating a sense of belonging and collective purpose. Because it can convey the idea that the candidate is not just an individual seeking power, but part of a larger group working towards common objectives. Here's the sample statement below.

"Requesting your support for team SERBISYONG TOTOO" (SK-10)

Emotive words. Are terms that evoke strong feelings or emotions in the reader or listener. Also, can have a significant impact during

election campaigns because they appeal to people's emotions, which can influence their perceptions and decision-making. Politicians particularly Sangguniang Kabataan often use emotive language to evoke strong feelings such as fear, hope, anger, or pride, to rally support for their candidacy or to discredit their opponents. However, the effectiveness of emotive language can vary depending on the context, audience, and credibility of the speaker. Overuse or misuse of emotive words can also backfire and alienate voters.

In the statement below were the emotive words manifested in the gathered corpora. The word "happy" is an emotive word, because it describes the feeling or emotions. When telling happy during election campaigns voters or listeners can integrate positive emotions. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use the word "happy" as campaign strategy because it can be an effective way to engage and motivate them. Here's the complete statement below.

"I'm very happy tungod kay anaa ang inyohang presensya" (SK-03)

(I'm very happy because your presence is here)

In connection, the statement below contains of emotive words which found in Sangguniang Kabataan. The term "Thank you" it can evoke positive feelings in the audience. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use the term emotive word like "thank you" during election campaigns as a strategy to evokes a positive impact on voters, because when candidates express gratitude, it can create a sense of appreciation and connection with the electorate. Therefore, by incorporating emotive words like "thank you" it can contribute to building rapport and trust between candidates and voters during election campaigns. In Sangguniang Kabataan they use the emotive words in that way.

"We're not just all talk, but we'll also act on this. Thank you for listening, and don't forget to vote us" (SK-05)

In addition, in the gathered corpora. The word "sad" is an emotive word which expresses of negative or unhappiness about the situation. In context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used the word "sad" as their strategy to make an emotional impact and it can drive higher voter turnout if people are moved to make a difference or make new perspective. Here's the complete sentence below.

"It so sad to say some people here are easily to buy tungod sa kwarta" (SK-08)

(It so sad to say some people here are easily to buy because of the cents)

Another, emotive words found in Sangguniang Kabataan. The word "confident" and "nervous." It conveys strong feelings and emotions related to self-assurance and anxiety, respectively. The "Confident" expresses a feeling of self-assurance and certainty, while "nervous" conveys a sense of anxiety or apprehension. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use these words as their strategy in order to evoke emotional responses from the audience and provide insight into the speaker's state of mind and attitude towards standing in front of others. In context of election campaigns confidence serves as an instilling trust and assurance in voters. While nervousness can prove to be a stumbling block for candidates. Also, excessive nervousness may consume credibility and undermine the perception of a candidate's ability to handle the pressures of leadership. Here's the complete statement below:

"I am confident standing in front of you without any nervous because kay kabalo ko sa akong sarili" (SK-09)

(I am confident standing in front of you without any nervous because I know myself)

Lastly, the words found in the statement below are "help," "motivated," and "difficulties." These words evoke feelings of support, encouragement, and challenges, which can inspire them to persevere in their studies. In context, during election campaigns the candidate they use the words "motivated" and "difficulties" because it can be a powerful tool to connect with voters on a personal level, appealing to their values and aspirations. It creates a sense of empathy and understanding, fostering a bond between the candidate and the voters. Additionally, using these words emotive language can help convey the candidate's sincerity and commitment to addressing the issues that matter most to voters, ultimately influencing their decision. The sample statement use in Sangguniang Kabataan is in the following:

"I just want to help the students here in barangay Bacasi so that they can be motivated to continue their studies despite whatever difficulties they may face" (SK-10)

Generalization. A rhetorical technique refers to the act of making sweeping and broad statements or assumptions about a situation, people, or ideas. In the realm of election campaigns, the use of generalization is prevalent and powerful. This approach involves crafting statements or claims that apply broadly to a diverse range of potential in audiences/voters. By doing so, Sangguniang Kabataan aim to create a sense of universality, suggesting that their objectives particularly their speeches fulfill a widespread need or desire to convey. In other words, it is employed by Sangguniang Kabataan to make voters feel part of a larger group, emphasizing the relationship between candidates and broad audience. On the other hand, it can also be used strategically to put a situation, people, or object in a negative light suggesting its belongingness to widespread undesirable events to attack an idea, situation, or person.

In connection, the statement below. The word "youth" serves as a generalizing term encompassing a broad range of individuals who may have differing perspectives, experiences, and priorities. As such, the statement "Vote for the youth" it lies in the implication that all youth should be supported based on their age group, without considering individual qualifications, beliefs, or capabilities. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this word "youth" in the statement as serves as a persuasive strategy by empowering young

people and emphasizing a future-oriented vision. Here's the complete statement in the following:

“Vote for the youth!” (SK-01)

Furthermore, the word "overall" It is used to encompass the entire platforms for addressing environmental and climate disasters under the "Natural Mind Academy". In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use the word "overall" because it can persuade during election campaigns in such a way to help candidates convey a sense of unity, collaboration, and inclusivity, all of which are important factors in persuading voters to support their candidacy. The use of the word “overall” in sample statement found in the following:

“Overall platforms for addressing environmental and climate disasters will be the “Natural Mind Academy”, consisting of seminars and workshops. Through collaboration with environmental organizations, NGOs, and university organizations, valuable information will be shared to aid in our efforts” (SK-03)

In addition, the sample statement below consists of generalization. The word “We” it refers to a collective group of people without specifying any individuals. It implies that the sentiment expressed applies universally to all individuals within that group, suggesting a general expectation. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the candidate uses the word “We” as to serves as a powerful tool to persuade voters and rally support in order to strengthen the connections with voter with giving a sense of hope and unity from the candidate. In the Sangguniang Kabataan they use the word “We” in the following:

“We should be open-minded to explore our ability or skills, because this is a step towards success” (SK-04)

Aside from that, the word “team” serves as a generalization because it refers to both specific teams mentioned (SULUGUON and Buagas). Thus, "team" functions as a generalization word, encompassing a broader category of teams beyond those explicitly stated. In context of during election campaigns the term "team" serves as a persuasive strategy, fostering unity and inclusivity among supporters and to reinforce their leadership role and inspire trust among voters, portraying themselves as capable leaders who can effectively coordinate efforts and candidates can mobilize their supporters, build a strong community, and increase their chances of electoral success. Moreover, in the statement Sangguniang Kabataan during election campaigns use the term “team” like this.

“Don’t forget us, the team (SULUGUON) and team Buagas” (SK-05)

Alliteration. The repetition of consonant sounds at the beginning of neighboring words, is a powerful rhetorical device often utilized in election campaigns to enhance memorability, create rhythm, and drive key messages home. Also, serves as a powerful tool in election campaigns, enabling candidates to craft memorable messages and convey their platforms with clarity and impact. By harnessing the rhythmic power of language, political hopefuls can leave a lasting impression on voters and increase their chances of electoral success. Moreover, in Sangguniang Kabataan alliteration effectively applied and seen.

In connection, the statement below which the alliteration effectively found. The term “Reduce, Reuse, recycle” the repetition is the letter “R” creates a rhythmic and memorable effect. Because the speakers incorporating environmental slogans like "Reduce, Reuse, recycle" into election campaigns it can be persuasive because speakers tap into voters' values, demonstrate a commitment to important issues, and present candidates as proactive leaders on environmental issues. Below is a sample statement found in Sangguniang Kabataan.

“Reduce, Reuse and Recycle Tree Planting Activity” (SK-03)

In addition, in the statement below alliteration were found. The words “go, glow and grow” in the sentence the alliteration is the repetition of “G” by repeating the sounds, the speaker use this kind of strategy because may the audience perceive that phrases and it will catch an attention and easier for them to remember such strategy words by the candidates. In the gathered corpora they use alliteration like this.

“I want our barangay like the vegetables have go, glow and grow” (SK-05)

Furthermore, the alliteration in the phrase "Sangguniang Kabataan Educational Support" is the repetition of the sound "S" in "Sangguniang" and "Support." Alliteration occurs when the same consonant sound is repeated at the beginning of neighboring or closely connected words. Therefore, the speaker uses this kind of strategy in order to leave unforgettable impact towards the audience, where it can find for them to easily remember because of its rhythm and memorable creativity. Here’s the complete statement below.

“SKES (Sangguniang Kabataan Educational Support) is for high school, senior high, and college students who are striving to achieve their dreams” (SK-07)

In addition, the alliteration in "senior supreme student council" is the repetition of the sound "s" in the words "senior", "supreme” and “student." Therefore, alliteration can greatly enhance the effectiveness of speech particularly in Sangguniang Kabataan during their election campaigns by improving its rhythm, making it more memorable, grabbing attention, and allowing for creative expression. The sample statements are the following:

“I became part of senior supreme student council” (SK-09)

Rhetorical questions. Is form of a question that is asked to make a point or to create an effect, but not require an actual answer. Also,

is to create a rhetorical effect which is mostly to engage the audience. Example, what's not to love about a beautiful sunset? this one evokes a sense of wonder and appreciation, inviting the audience to share the sentiment. Aside from that, rhetorical questions are often used in persuasive communication to engage the audience, create a sense of involvement, and lead them to a specific conclusion or perspective. In the context, in Sangguniang Kabataan these questions can serve to challenge opposing viewpoints or encourage voters to consider alternative perspectives, furthering the persuasive impact of the campaigns because it is a powerful tool for candidates seeking to engage, persuade, and ultimately win over during the election campaigns.

In connection, the use of rhetorical questions was found in the gathered corpora. The phrase "where's the budget?" this statement is not highlighting about finding the money or budget, in which the speakers talk about dissatisfaction or confusion about the lack of information regarding the budget before. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used these questions as effective strategy because they prompt the audience to think critically about the issue at hand and consider the perspective. Therefore, the phrase as rhetorical questions used by the candidate it can be a powerful tool in persuasive communication because it engages the audience and encourage them to reflect on their own beliefs and values.

"Because I know the issues here in the community, I am running for councilor. It was really quiet before, very quiet! It's true, it was quiet! Where's the budget?" (SK-01)

In addition, another rhetorical question found in gathered corpora. The question "Where's the peace they promised before?" it is used to express frustration rather than to elicit direct answer. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this rhetorical question during election campaigns as to questioning the absence of promised peace. Therefore, by using this question it can motivate to the people to demand change or seek solutions for this problem. Here's the complete sample statement in the following:

"Where's the peace they promised before?" (SK-03)

Furthermore, another rhetorical question found in Sangguniang Kabataan. "Are you willing to vote us?" This question is simply to ask question for the audience if they are willing to vote their team. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this rhetorical question as to engage the audience and prompt them to consider their support for the mentioned "team Sulugon and Buagas" even without certain respond. Below is the sample statement found in Sangguniang Kabataan.

"Hoping this upcoming election, you will vote the team Sulugon and the team Buagas. Are you willing to vote us?" (SK-05)

Aside from that, the rhetorical questions found in Sangguniang Kabataan is "Are you willing to change your principles for just 300 pesos?" This question is designed to provoke thought and to persuade the audience by appealing to their sense of moral integrity and values. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this rhetorical question as to engage to the audience and emphasize the importance of sticking to one's principles, even in the face of temptation. The candidates are trying to aim to persuade voters by appealing to their sense of morality and integrity. Below is the sample statement.

"But don't sell your principles. Are you willing to change your principles for just 300 pesos?" (SK-06)

Aside from that, the rhetorical question is "don't forget us?" it is literal requesting to the audience, this rhetorical question "don't forget us?" is a request for someone to remember or not to overlook a person or group to vote their opponents. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this kind of strategic question in order to request to vote them and not overlook other opponents, but its only them. However, it can also be used rhetorically to imply a deeper meaning or to make a point rather than to seek an actual response. Here's the complete sentence below.

"This upcoming election, don't forget us?" (SK-04)

Another rhetorical question is "Unsa may mahitabo sa council kung walay involvement sa kabatan-onan?" This question is meant to provoke thought and engage the audience by implying that the council's future might be at risk without the participation of youth. Therefore, upon examining the rhetorical questions found in the Sangguniang Kabataan it highlights an effective persuasive tool during election campaigns, helping candidates to engage voters, convey their message, and influence opinions without coming across as overly forceful or aggressive. Below is the statement used in Sangguniang Kabataan.

"Unsa may mahitabo sa council kung walay involvement sa kabatan-onan?" (SK-10)

(But what will happen to the council if there is no youth's involvement?)

Connotation. Refers to the meaning suggested by a word or thing in addition to its explicit meaning or to implied emotional meaning of a word beyond its literal meaning. Example, the word "home" connotes warmth, security, and family, while its literal meaning is just a place where someone lives. Therefore, using connotation can vary depending on the context, but in the context of Sangguniang Kabataan connotation was utilized for persuading to make it memorable in the listeners particularly in the voters.

In this study was used connotation particularly found in the gathered corpora. In the phrase "Our barangay is our second home" is the connotation because it implies a deep attachment in the community, it tells that "Barangay" is not just simply place but it significant where people feel safe and valued. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used that phrases to create an emotional connection and making voters feel that the candidate genuinely understands and cares about their local issues. Here's the complete sentence below.

“Our barangay is our second home. It is important to preserves the cleanliness and securities” (SK-01)

Moreover, the phrase “glimpse of lights” also considered as connotation and it relates to the phrase “feeling the color”, this phrase tells a something positive and hopeful, and doesn’t talk about seeing lights, in which the phrase is not literally saying the meaning, but it takes a deep meaning. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the speaker uses that phrase as strategy to convey the message and express that they are being hopeful and glad to give lights for their barangay in the future. However, in the gathered corpora they used that phrase in the following:

“I feel the color today, you know why? Because I already see the Glimpse of lights here in our barangay” (SK-03)

In addition, another connotation found in the gathered corpora. The phrase “brought me here’ is considered as connotation because it implies speaker’s confidence played a crucial role. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used that strategy to express their feelings towards the audience and the confidence referring to speaker is not only talking about feeling but enable to achieve their current success. Here’s the complete statement below.

“My confidence brought me here to stand on the stage” (SK-05)

Moreover, the phrase “spread love” and “ugly” is the connotation in the sentence because in the past the community was feel bad. Therefore, the love is also connotation because is needed in order to solve the current state problem. Upon analyzing the statement, the speaker uses the past experienced as persuasive strategy to highlights the issue and this time they make it solution. In the gathered corpora they used that connotation below.

“Let’s spread love because it is so ugly that the community of barangay can’t find peace like before” (SK-07)

Anecdotes. Is a short, interesting, and often humorous story about a real incident or person. It's usually based on personal experiences or observations. Also, it plays a crucial role in election campaigns particularly in Sangguniang Kabataan by shaping narratives, connecting candidates with voters, and influencing public opinion. Therefore, when using anecdotes, it is effective because it shares personal stories which can create a sense of connection, and it can be powerful tools for winning hearts and minds on the campaign trail or towards the voters.

In connection, in the statement below found in Sangguniang Kabataan considered as anecdote because it recounts a personal experience or story. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this anecdote as persuasive strategy specifically about the speaker's grandfather and the values he imparted, the speaker is trying to share the importance of genuine service for future prospects of the youth, and valuing goodness of heart over material wealth, all through the lens of the speaker's grandfather's teachings and experiences as a vice mayor, with that it have huge impact both speaker and audience and it leaves memorable and impactful message. Here’s the complete statement in the following:

“Gitudloan ko sa akong lolo, nga kaniadtong vice mayor pa siya diri sa New Corella, ang kahinungdanon sa tinuod nga pagserbisyo daw. Iyang ingon nga ang tinuod nga bahandi dili masukod sa kadako sa bank account, kundi sa pagkamaayo sa atong kasingkasing. Kinahanglan natong unahon ang kaayohan ug ang kaugmaon sa mga batan-on” (SK-06)

(I was taught by my grandfather, who was vice mayor before here in New Corella, the importance of genuine service and suggests that true wealth is measured by the goodness of one’s heart rather than the size of bank account. It is needed to prioritize the well-being and future prospect of the youth)

Another anecdote was found in the gathered corpora. In the context of father’s experience as barangay captain, turning it into an anecdote because involves focusing on a specific story or event that highlights his values or lessons learned. Aside from that, the speaker using this kind of strategy to illustrates his perspective on leadership and responsibility, the listener or audience can create a memorable anecdote that effectively conveys the essence of his story. Here’s the complete statement below.

“Sa dihang nagserbisyo ang akong amahan isip barangay captain, kanunay niyang ginasulti ang daghang responsibilidad nga dala sa maong papel. Usa ka istorya nga iyang gishare mao ang bahin sa usa ka kalihokan sa komunidad nga nahimong kalibog tungod sa kalit nga kusog nga ulan. Bisan pa sa kalibog, nagpabilin siyang kalmado, nagtukod ug nakig-coordinate sa mga boluntaryo aron ibalhin ang tanan sa sulod sa balay ug masiguro nga ang tanan luwas ug komportable. Ang iyang dedikasyon dili tungod sa pagpaningkamot nga makakuha ug kasikat o pagkilala; kini mahitungod sa tinuod nga pag-atiman sa mga tawo nga iyang ginaserbisyoan. Pinaagi sa mga hagit nga iyang naagian, gitudloan niya ako nga ang liderato mao ang pag-una sa uban ug ang pagpangita ug solusyon bisan pa sa labing lisud nga mga sitwasyon” (SK-10)

(When my father served as barangay captain, he often spoke about the huge of responsibility that came with the role. One story he shared was about a community event that went awry due to unexpected heavy rain. Despite the chaos, he stayed calm, coordinating with volunteers to move everything indoors and ensure everyone was safe and comfortable. His dedication wasn’t about seeking fame or recognition; it was about genuinely caring for the people he served. Through these challenges, he taught me that leadership is about putting others first and finding solutions even in the most difficult situations)

Appeals. Another persuasive technique is the use of appeals especially the use of a variety of emotional appeals to persuade the

audience. These are the feelings and emotions that the speaker wants to arouse in their listeners. Appeals are a potent tool in the art of persuasion, particularly during speech election campaigns of candidates particularly in Sangguniang Kabataan. These appeals often target voters' emotions, values, and beliefs to influence their decisions. Overall, effective election campaigns often incorporate a combination of these persuasive appeals to engage voters and win their support. Therefore, successful candidates understand the values of their target audience and tailor their messaging accordingly to maximize their persuasive impact.

In connection, in the given statement, the speaker used emotional appeal to emphasize appeals to many because it speaks to the belief that our actions are guided by a higher power giving them a sense of purpose and direction. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this strategy to remind people of their duty to obey divine commands, which can provide comfort during tough times and help them make sense of right and wrong. Plus, it strengthens bonds within religious communities, as they share a common belief in following God's guidance. Overall, it offers a simple yet powerful explanation for what we do. Here's the complete statement below:

“We are only running because we are commanded by the Almighty” (SK-01)

Furthermore, in the statement below, was considered as appeals. The phrase “bring us good luck and fortune” is all about something positive, because it makes essentially based on positive outcomes or benefits associated with voting in a certain way. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this kind of appeal as persuasive strategy to aim and persuade people by emphasizing how their choice results are important. In the gathered corpora they use this appeal through the following:

“Your votes bring us good luck and fortune, especially in our barangay” (SK-02)

Another, statement using persuasive techniques of appeals. The statement below being provided appeals to a sense of social responsibility and empathy. It addresses a pressing issue of violence against women and children, which unfortunately remains predominant in many environments. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this strategy by expressing a desire to organize a symposium aimed at empowering victims to stand up for their rights, was speaker demonstrate a commitment to taking action and creating positive change. This initiative would likely resonate with many individuals particularly the speakers who are concerned about social justice and equality. Here's the statement in the following:

“Violent Against Women and Children, this kind of case are dominant in our barangay. If I will win, I would like to implement a symposium at our school to aimed and empowering these victims to stand up for their rights” (SK-06)

Furthermore, in the statement below, an emotional appeal was found in the gathered corpora effectively employed using goal. The speaker was expressing positive emotions and aspirations in the youth. Therefore, the statement shows an appeal which to a broad audience by emphasizing inclusivity and equality. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the speaker stating about the goal which to create opportunities for all youth to participate in events, regardless of their strengths in sports or academics, the speaker demonstrating a commitment to diversity and providing equal access to opportunities. Therefore, this inclusive approach is likely to resonate positively with many people who support such values.

“I aim to prioritize inclusivity and equality in my platforms. My goal is to create opportunities for all youth to participate in every event, not just those who good in sports, but also those who good in education games” (SK-09)

Lastly, the statement below, the speaker employed a persuasive strategy by appealing to the audience's social responsibility and compassion. It acknowledges the struggles faced by many youths, particularly in difficult circumstances, and expresses a desire to help their hardships. By praying for guidance and seeking to establish programs to support youth, especially in meeting their basic needs and encouraging education. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this strategy to express a sincere effort to address the challenges they face and promote their well-being. With that, the speaker was demonstrated a commitment to serving the community and fostering positive change. Here's the sample statement in the following:

“I have noticed that many youths are dropping out of school because life is really hard, especially here as a SK council we pray to God to allow us to provide programs that can help the youth, at least to provide for their basic needs and of course to encourage them to continue their studies” (SK-10)

Hyperbole is a figure of speech in which exaggeration is used for emphasis or effect. It is not meant to be taken literally. Another words, hyperbole is a persuasive strategy that involves exaggerating certain aspects of a message to make a point more emphatically. It's a common rhetorical device used in various forms of communication, including advertising, politics, literature, and everyday conversation. Again, in hyperbole, statements are exaggerated or overstated to create a more vivid or dramatic effect. For example, saying "I'm so hungry I could eat a horse" or "I've told you a million times" are both examples of hyperbole. Hyperbole is commonly used in literature, poetry, and everyday language to add emphasis, humor, or to make a point more forcefully.

In connection, the sample statement below, which are the gathered data from the Sangguniang Kabataan were utilizing the hyperbole. The statement “It was really quiet before, very quiet!” This is an exaggerated statement meant to the speaker which is emphasizing just how silent things were in the past, likely to highlight the dramatic change they're now trying to address by running for councilor and focusing on youth issues. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this term “very quiet” as to exaggerate in which to help to convey the speaker's message effectively. The speaker was intended to capture the attention of the audience, to make the message

memorable, and evoke a sense of importance, ultimately by persuading people to support the speaker's campaign for councilor and youth engagement. The sample statement being refer is in the following:

“Because I know the issues here in the community, it was really quiet before, very quiet! It's true, it was quiet! Where's the budget? That's true, not a joke, but now we're running for the Youth” (SK-01)

Furthermore, another sample statement using the hyperbole was found in the gathered corpora. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this phrase “a million times” as an exaggerated statement and claim not meant to be taken literally as to a way of stressing the importance of voting passionately and frequently and where the phrase was creating a strong impression towards the voters. The sample statement is in the following:

“Youth there, I will tell you a million times. Vote with all your hearts” (SK-03)

Aside from that, another sample statement where the use of hyperbole effectively seen in Sangguniang Kabataan election campaigns. The phrase “I have a lot of action than words” is an exaggerated statement and claim not meant to be taken literally. The candidate was used extreme exaggerates than the amount of action compared to something were suggesting an imbalance in favor of action. The candidate employing hyperbole as strategy to emphasize a lot of action than words, the speaker persuades the audience to value and prioritize action, implying that the speaker is someone who backs up their words with strong beliefs. The statement is in the following:

“I have a lot of action than words” (SK-05)

On the other hand, another hyperbole also manifested in the gathered corpora. The phrase “this opportunity is impossible” is an exaggerating idea. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this phrase tell how difficult or out of reach it feels, even though it might not be literally impossible. The sample statement is in the following:

“I am introvert person this opportunity is impossible” (SK-06)

Lastly, another hyperbole was found in the gathered corpora. The phrase “sell out for a few cents” is an exaggerated way, were the speaker used this kind of hyperbole as persuasive techniques because in the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used that phrase to express how easily people might betray their principles or values for very little reward during election day, upon hearing those message may the voters will awake the truthfulness and they vote the candidate who are truly qualified in that certain position. The sample statement is in the following:

“People here would sell out for a few cents!” (SK-08)

Colloquial language. Colloquial language is a language that is used in everyday situations. it's essential to use colloquial language as sense and consider audience and the context in which speakers communicating. While it can be effective in many situations, there may be times when a more formal tone is more appropriate. However, it's important for politicians to strike a balance with colloquial language. While it can be effective in connecting with voters, using too much slang or informal language may come across as unprofessional or disrespectful, especially in formal settings or when discussing serious issues. Additionally, politicians should ensure that their message remains clear and coherent, even when using colloquial language, to avoid any misunderstandings or misinterpretations.

In connection, in the statement below found in Sangguniang Kabataan they effectively use the persuasive techniques the colloquial language. The term "Sana all" is a Filipino colloquial phrase it refers wishing or hoping everyone. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this term as to appeal to voters' desires or aspirations. Also, it's a casual and informal expression depending in the context but this term is a colloquial language because it commonly used in everyday conversations. Here's the complete sentence below.

“No more sana all. Yes, to team UNLAD you will sure” (SK-01)

In addition, employing colloquial language such as " Mga Madi" considered as a group name or friends and used as persuasive strategy during election campaigns, particularly when targeting the youth demographic. The term “Mga Madi” is a colloquial language found only in the specific area in the Philippines and this term is very known in the particular community, the candidate uses this term as to call the people out there particularly those who listened during their campaigns. Here's the complete statement in the following:

“Good evening Mga Madi! Thank you for coming” (SK-02)

(Good evening, friends! Thank you for coming)

Furthermore, using colloquial language in election campaigns can be an effective persuasive strategy to connect with voters on a personal level. The term "werpa" is considered as colloquial language and informal words, also it is an opposite term of “power” as it refers to the energy or class. The term “werpa” also heard in the specific area of the Philippines. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this term, to persuade the listeners since this is unique word where the audience heard the word “werpa” it leaves impactful meaning and uniqueness. In the gathered corpora they use that term like this.

“Vote team SULUGUON kay naa na ang werpa na ready mo tabang sa mga Kabataan” (SK-03)

(Vote for team SULUGUON because they have the power and ready to help the youth)

Moreover, using term like "lodi" also known as idol upon reversing that term it can indeed and became an effective colloquial strategy in election campaigns. That term was only found or heard in the specific area and by addressing that in the audience it is informal language. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this term to aim to grab attention and create a sense of importance around their message. This term can motivate individuals and can ultimately benefit and uniqueness of the candidate who employs such language. Here's the complete statement below:

"Ako diay si Ramon Chatto Jr. ang lodi sa team suluguon" (SK-05)

(I am Ramon Chatto Jr. is the idol of Team Suluguon)

Aside from that, using colloquial language like the use of "Inday" and "dodong" as terms of endearment for young girls and boys and this informal conversational tone are key markers of colloquial language. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used these terms as persuasive strategy to call by their respective sex, upon hearing those it can a direct appeal to everyday people, as showing respect for their role in the election process and reinforcing the candidate's connection to the community. Below is the statement found in Sangguniang Kabataan.

"Mga inday og dodong diha sa kilid kilid ayaw tawon ninyo kalimti mi sa umaabot na election" (SK-06)

(Young ladies and gentlemen in the neighborhoods, please don't forget us in the upcoming election)

Analogy. An analogy is a rhetorical device used to explain or clarify a concept by comparing it to something else that is more familiar or easily understood. It involves drawing parallels between two different things to highlight similarities and help the audience grasp the intended meaning. However, it's important to note that the effectiveness of analogies in election campaigns depends on various factors such as the audience's receptiveness, the context in which they are used, and the credibility of the candidate delivering them. But analogies can be a powerful tool for persuasion, they should be used a sense and ethically to avoid misleading or manipulating voters.

In connection, an analogy is a comparison between two things that are usually dissimilar but share some common characteristics. The phrase "life is like a box of chocolate" is an analogy because "life" is compared to "box of chocolate" to illustrate that idea, is that life is full of surprises, and you can't predict what will happen next. Upon analyzing the phrase is not literal taken a meaning which it is kind of logic it must understand what it means for. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this phrase as persuasive strategy to tell voters to vote with all hearts and to think who will be capable of that certain position, this strategy is to connects also between candidate and voters' life and have strong connection. In the gathered corpora they use that term in the following:

"You just must vote with all your hearts why? Because someone says that life is like a box of chocolate. You never know what you're gonna get" (SK-02)

Moreover, another example of analogy was effectively seen in the gathered corpora. The phrase "Eyes are to seeing as ears are to hearing" is an analogy because in the statement, it compares the function of eyes and ears to the function of witnesses in a situation also tells that just as eyes and ears have specific roles in perceiving events and witnesses and have a role in understanding what happened. In context of Sangguniang Kabataan the speaker used these phrases to convey the essential message especially telling that voters must vote to the certain person or who are the capable for that position. This comparison helps emphasize the importance of making informed and also it can give lesson to the voters. Here's the sample statement below:

"Kabalo nata daan kung unsa ang mahitabo sa atong barangay, we have eyes and ears who witnessed sa tanan, our eyes are to seeing as ears are to hearing. Therefore, please vote wisely" (SK-04)

(We are already known what was happened to our barangay, we have eyes and ears who witnessed everything, our eyes are to seeing as ears are to hearing. Therefore, please vote wisely)

In addition, the phrase "education is like a power" is considered as analogy because the "education" was compared to different aspects but similar others. As such, by comparing the education to a power it highlights how education can be a transformative force and how the power can drive change. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used these phrases as persuasive strategy to connect emotionally and intellectually with voters, by empowering through education, speaker use this phrase as persuasive techniques as make it more memorable. Here's the complete sentence below.

"Education is like a power that we can use to change the world" (SK-09)

Aside from that, the term "winning is a joy as losing is a defeat" is an example of analogy. Because it compares the outcomes of election may winning or losing or it may joy or defeat. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this term as their persuasive strategy; to tell their feelings to the audience and taking risks for the meantime, the speaker may find helpful for them to persuade the voter by expressing their emotions. Here's the sample statement in the following:

"Para sa umaabot na election kung unsa man ang resulta I can say that winning is a joy as losing is a defeat, I will remain to choose the

acceptance, at least I try” (SK-10)

(For upcoming election what will be the outcome of it I can say that winning is a joy as losing is a defeat, I will remain to choose the acceptance, at least I try)

Simile. Way to compare things is to highlight similarities. It plays a significant role in conveying meaning and adding depth to communication. Similes are used to make descriptions more vivid and imaginative by drawing comparisons between unrelated concepts usually using the words "like" or "as." Also, similes serve as powerful tools in election campaigns, allowing to shape public perception to their advantage. Whether used to highlight strengths, draw comparisons, or evoke emotions. In addition, similes play a crucial role in influencing voters and ultimately determining the outcome of an election.

In connection, in the statement below was another sample of simile. The phrase “Our barangay is like our home” is a simile because it compares “barangay” to the “home” using by “like” as comparative marker by illustrating the similarity between the two. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use this phrase as a persuasive strategy to tell that if the speaker wins this election, they will take care the barangay just like a home. Here’s the complete statement below:

“Our barangay is like our home; we need to take care of it” (SK-02)

Moreover, the “Ang mga kabatan-onan mura’g adlaw nga nagdala ug kahayag sa komunidad” is an example of simile because youth was compared to the sun (adlaw) which emphasize how they bring energy and lights to the community, when comparing the two things it was use “mura’g” in English translation “like” as comparative marker. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used these phrases to persuade voter by portraying and saying that the youth are the hopes and the lights of everything. Here’s the complete sentence that found in the gathered corpora.

“Ang mga kabatan-onan mura’g adlaw nga nagdala ug kahayag sa komunidad” (SK-04)

(You know what we youth is like a sun who bring lights to the community)

In addition, another simile was found in the gathered corpora. The speaker was employed simile. The phrase “Ang kabatan-onan mao ang nagahimo sama sa kalambuan” it compares to the phrase “sama sa mga bitoon nga nagagiya kanato sa dalan sa kalibog ug kawalay” the word "sama" in Bisaya term or “like” in English term is used to establish a comparison between the youth and bright stars as a comparative marker. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used these phrases to persuade just like to tell that the youth is like a brighter star who play a guiding role during uncertain times. The comparison emphasizes the importance and significance of the youth in shaping the future. Here’s the sample statement in the following:

“Ang kabatan-onan mao ang nagahimo sama sa kalambuan, sama sa mga bitoon nga nagagiya kanato sa dalan sa kalibog ug kawalay kasigurohan” (SK-06)

(The youth are the threads that weave the fabric of progress, like bright stars guiding path through the darkness of uncertainty)

Furthermore, in the statements below, speakers effectively employed simile. The Sangguniang Kabataan during election campaigns they use these phrases to compare the “Ang SK chairman” to the phrase “sama sa ka lig-on nga kahoy nga nagabarug bisan sa tunga sa bagyo” by using “sama” in Bisaya term or “like” as a comparative marker. Therefore, the speaker portrayed as providing stability, support, and resilience. It suggests that the SK chairman plays a central role in maintaining stability and guiding the organization even the challenging times, much like a tree provides shelter and protection during a storm. Therefore, the phrases were used by the speaker it serves as a powerful persuasive technique during election campaigns by framing the candidate as a leader and capable of navigating challenges and providing stability to the community. Here’s the complete statement below.

“Ang SK chairman sama sa ka lig-on nga kahoy nga nagabarug bisan sa tunga sa bagyo, kanunay nga gagiya ug suporta para sa iyang mga kauban” (SK-09)

(An SK chairman is like a sturdy tree in the midst of a storm)

In addition, another simile was found in the gathered corpora. The phrase "our unity shines like a beacon, as strong as a fortress," the words, "like a beacon" compares the shining quality of unity to the guiding light of a beacon, and "as strong as a fortress" it compares the strength of unity to the resilience of a fortress. While, "like" serves the function of simile and create vivid imagery and enhance the voters understanding by likening the qualities of unity to those of a beacon and a fortress. In context of Sangguniang Kabataan they use these phrases as persuasive strategy during election campaigns to effectively reinforces the candidate's message of unity and strength, compelling voters to align themselves with the vision in the future. As the power of imagery, it leaves a lasting impression and support behind the campaigns. Here's the complete statement below:

“Sa kalisod nga atong panag-uban ming gaan sama sa suga nga nagabuhat sa atong dalan. Kusgan kaayo ta sama sa pader, nagtinabangay sa pag-atubang sa tanan natong mga hagit” (SK-10)

(In the face of adversity, our unity shines like a beacon, as strong as a fortress guiding us through storm of challenges)

Imagery. On the other note, imagery refers to the use of descriptive language that appeals to the senses, evoking mental images,

sensations, or experiences for the reader or listener. Imagery functions at the semantic level by providing mental representations that aid in understanding, memory, communication, and emotional processing of abstract concepts and meanings. Also, it plays a multifaceted role in SK election campaigns, serving as a means to increase candidate visibility, convey messages effectively, and shape public perception to ultimately secure voter support.

In connection, in the gathered data which the imagery was effectively seen in Sangguniang Kabataan. The phrase “very quiet” which painting a picture with words, invoking the sense of hearing and creating a mental image of silence. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used these terms “very quiet” to invites the voters to imagine how quiet were the former candidate during their administration causing of not good outcomes, this strategy is making it a powerful tool for creating vivid imagery in conversation. Therefore, the strategic use of these terms it captures voters' attention and inspire hope for positive change under their leadership. Here's the sample statement in the following:

“Because I know the issues here in the community, I am running for councilor. It was really quiet before very quiet! It's true, it was quiet! Where's the budget? That's true, not a joke, but now we're running for the Youth” (SK-01)

Moreover, another imagery was found in the gathered corpora. The word “lights” is an imagery because it creates a vivid mental picture of the impact of the youth in the barangay. Also, the "light" can symbolize positivity, or a bright future brought by the youth. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this word “Lights” as their persuasive strategy to convey and create a hopeful future to the voters and barangay. Here's the complete sentence below.

“I see the light of our barangay because of the youth here!” (SK-02)

“You know what we youth is like a sun who bring lights to the community” (SK-04)

Aside from that, another used of imagery also found in the gathered corpora. The phrase “I already smell” it creates picture in listener's mind and metaphorical. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this phrase as their strategy to tell an intuitive sense or a prediction about the outcome. Apart from that, it's not literally about smelling but rather about sensing or predicting success. Here's the complete statement below:

“I already smell, that if you will vote team Sulugon you will never get disappoint by choosing us” (SK-07)

In addition, the phrase “smile bright” it evokes imagery by creating a mental picture of someone smiling brightly and the idea of maintaining brightness intact. Also, it describes a sense of cherishing and protecting something joyful and positive. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this phrase during election campaigns as the strategy through evoking emotions of hope, positivity, and unity while highlighting the importance of youth empowerment and community support. Here's the complete statement in the following:

“Preserve the smile bright” (SK-08)

Furthermore, the phrase "change the color" is an imagery because it uses a visual metaphor to convey a deeper idea, and it creates a vivid picture of how one's actions can lead to significant change. In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan they used this phrase as to convey the message to suggest a desire to move away from the past administration of the candidate and to change new political direction. Here's the complete statement below:

“Your vote will change the color of our barangay, what I mean is to change the future” (SK-10)

Assonance. Refers to the repetition of vowel sounds within nearby words in a sentence or phrase. Assonance, as a persuasive strategy in election campaigns, relies on the repetition of vowel sounds within words to create a rhythmic and memorable effect. This technique enhances the candidate's message by making it more emotionally impactful and easier to remember. For example, a slogan like “A Better Future for All” utilizes assonance with the repeated “uh” sound in “better” and “future,” creating a sense of unity and optimism.

In connection, in the given statement below which found in Sangguniang Kabataan, the persuasive techniques which is the assonance was effectively utilized. The assonance in the statement “United we stand, hand in hand, to demand a brighter land” is found in the repetition of the vowel sound “a” in the words “stand,” “hand,” and “demand.” In the context of Sangguniang Kabataan the repetition it creates a sense of rhythm and harmony within the phrase and emphasizing the unity and solidarity conveyed by the message. The use of assonance here not only enhances the message or speeches quality of the statement but also reinforces its theme of togetherness and collective action for a better future. Here's the complete statement in the following:

“United we stand, hand in hand, to demand a brighter land” (SK-02)

Furthermore, the assonance in the statement “Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle Tree Planting Activity” it lies in the repetition of the “ee” sound in the words “Reduce,” “Reuse,” and “Tree.” In the context of election campaigns, this assonance can be effectively used to create a memorable and catchy slogan. The repetition of the “ee” sound not only makes the statement rhythmic and pleasing to the ear but also reinforces the message of environmental conservation.

“Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle Tree Planting Activity” (SK-03)

Moreover, another assonance found in the gathered corpora. The words “go, glow and grow” is an example of assonance because of the repeated “o” sound in “go,” “glow,” and “grow” then it creates a rhythmic and memorable effect. Using this kind of assonance in the election campaign speech may the speaker can find a helpful strategy through creating a positive and memorable impression that aligns with the goals or values that want to promote. Here’s the complete sentence below.

“I want our barangay like the vegetables have go, glow and grow” (SK-05)

Lastly, the assonance in the statement below “Negosyo mo, paunlarin mo” lies in the repetition of the vowel sound “o” in the words “negosyo” and “mo”, as well as in “paunlarin” and “mo”. Assonance is a literary device that involves the repetition of vowel sounds within nearby words or phrases. In the context of election campaigns, this phrase can be effectively used to resonate with voters by appealing to their aspirations for economic progress and prosperity. The repetition of the vowel sound “o” creates a memorable slogan that can stick in the minds of the voters. Additionally, the use of assonance in this slogan enhances its effectiveness in capturing attention and conveying a compelling message during election campaigns.

“Negosyo mo, paunlarin mo” (SK-04)

Conclusions

This study aims to show why it is crucial to understand the language specifically the linguistic features used by Sangguniang Kabataan during election campaigns. Aside from that, it is crucial to know also the various persuasive techniques they employ. Additionally, it emphasizes how analyzing their speeches can help improve language teaching. By using real-life examples like transcripts and videos, where educators can enhance students' listening, speaking, and understanding abilities. Furthermore, it helps expand vocabulary by identifying and incorporating specific words and phrases used by Sangguniang Kabataan, aiding in language learning tailored to relevant contexts.

The study highlights also the importance of teaching practical communication skills, especially in persuading others. It helps learners grasp how language works in various situations like politics, school, social gatherings, work or any kind of fields. It also encourages critical thinking by analyzing how young leaders persuade people, urging learners to think carefully about the information they receive. Additionally, it boosts awareness of different cultures and how language is used, helping learners communicate better across cultures.

This study can really benefit in Sangguniang Kabataan. It gives useful information about language and convincing methods. So, politicians can learn from it to improve how they talk to people. This helps them make better and more confident during speeches, that will capture people's interest or voters and get them involved.

Furthermore, the study’s focus on vocabulary expansion is valuable for young politicians or Sangguniang Kabataan. Therefore, by incorporating the vocabulary items and phrases identified in this study, politicians can add and expand their specific vocabulary and terminology, with that it helps them too aware by using the words or phrases. Moreover, this allows them to accurately and persuasively convey their message towards the audiences or voters like improving their ability to communicate the unique features and benefits of their speech. Aside from that, this can have a positive impact on campaign period.

Additionally, the practical skills part of this research is really helpful for youth councils or Sangguniang Kabataan. It helps them learn how to use language correctly when they talk, so they can adjust how they communicate to who they're talking to. This means using polite ways of speaking, persuasive techniques, and avoiding saying negative things about others. Getting better at this stuff makes politicians better at running for election, which means they're more likely to win when they campaign.

On the other hand, this study contributes to the literature on political aspects as it provides insights into effective language use in election campaigns. By examining the language patterns and persuasive techniques employed by Sangguniang Kabataan, this research study deepens understanding of how linguistics features, including morphology, semantics, and syntax, can strategically utilized to influence the audiences/voters in order for them to make own decisions to vote. These new ideas make the existing studies about influencing better by giving a detailed look at how language is important in political communication that works well.

Furthermore, this can be contributing to enhancing the teaching and understanding of political communication, especially in the context of election campaigns or campaign period. This research may impart significant perspectives for educators and students aiming to improve their communication strategies in the field of teaching especially for the future educators, ultimately leading to more effective and persuasive teaching techniques.

Moreover, this study identifies and analyzes persuasive strategies specific to the political aspects. This contributes to the political literature by expanding knowledge of persuasive techniques employed by successful young politicians’ endeavors. The findings shed light on how Sangguniang Kabataan employ language to build trust, create a sense of urgency, address objections and decision making. This knowledge is valuable for politicians and researchers as it provides a foundation for developing targeted and persuasive communication strategies within during the election campaigns. As well as the practical implications of this study benefit for political aspects. By understanding the linguistics features and persuasive strategies identified in the research, every politician can apply this knowledge to enhance and their desire during election campaign efforts. They can adopt and adapt the effective language techniques employed by successful politician to engage their target audience, through influence and entertain. The study bridges the gap between

theoretical understanding and practical application in the field of political aspects.

Aside from that, this research study can contribute to promoting transparency and protection. Through analyzing the language used by Sangguniang Kabataan, this study sheds lights on the persuasive techniques employed during election campaigns. This knowledge can be used to educate future politicians about common persuasive tactics, enabling them to make more informed decisions. By increasing political awareness and understanding of these strategies, this study helps empower individuals to navigate transactions confidently and avoid potential negative information against to other parties, and unethical practices.

Furthermore, this research could reveal possible ethical issues connected to how language is used to influence people during election campaigns. By examining the linguistic techniques and persuasive methods used by Sangguniang Kabataan, we can better understand what's happening. This understanding can help us talk about how to run campaigns responsibly and give policymakers ideas for making rules that keep politicians safe while ensuring fairness and ethics in elections.

Also, this research can contribute to promoting critical thinking skills. This study encourages individuals to think critically about the information they encounter or hear in election period. This can help individuals develop skills necessary to discern between authentic and misleading campaign tactics. By promoting critical thinking skills, this study contributes to empowering individuals to make informed choices and resist potential manipulation during in election campaign context.

This research study has successfully attained its main objectives which were to explore the linguistic features and persuasive strategies used by Sangguniang Kabataan during election campaigns. It has been presented that upon the analysis data, information has been presented well and explanations have been provided in connection to the inquiry of this undertaking. In as much as this study is limited only to the analysis of 10 speeches of Sangguniang Kabataan. The following recommendations for future research are hereby presented.

Since this study focused on the analysis of linguistics features and persuasive strategies manifested in Sangguniang Kabataan during election campaigns, future may still be conducted along this line. With that, future researchers may replicate this research study but with a larger dataset they may gathered 10 above. Furthermore, it is highly recommended to increase the number of corpora to be used to verify or refute the findings gathered also to know more about the linguistic features and persuasive strategies will be used. In connection, they are highly welcome and encourage to apply the same research approach or even to try other approaches, or somehow, gather corpora from other platforms that conduct online or face to face events. Besides, the linguistics features of the study may focus on any other means that were exhausted but moderate only in this study that may lead to the understanding of linguistic features and persuasive strategies inherent during election campaigns.

Moreover, in order to have an advance field of linguistic features and persuasive strategies in speeches particularly in election campaigns, future research should focus on several key areas. Firstly, there is a need for an in-depth exploration of the specific linguistic features, including morphology, semantics, and syntax, that contribute to persuasive language in speech election campaigns. Through detailed analysis of these features, researchers can uncover their impact on voter/audiences' behavior and their effectiveness in different speech campaign contexts. By understanding the underlying mechanisms of persuasive language, scholars can provide valuable perspective for politicians aiming to optimize their communication strategies.

Additionally, another essential area future research is the investigation or exploration of language adaptation in speeches used by Sangguniang Kabataan. It is essential to understand how Sangguniang Kabataan adapt their language persuasive strategies to effectively engage and influence to the audiences or voters. By examining how young politicians modify their language to accommodate cultural norms, preferences, and communication styles, researchers can contribute to the development of guidelines and equal best practices for successful election campaign period.

To gain a comprehensive understanding of persuasive language used by Sangguniang Kabataan or their persuasive speeches, future research should also consider longitudinal studies that track the relationship over extended period between the important persons. By analyzing how persuasive language influences in order the audiences/ voters will effectively captures their attention.

Furthermore, discourse analysis across the different studies which related to the study that I have or platforms it can provide valuable insights into persuasive language use. By exploring linguistic features and persuasive strategies, researchers can identify similarities and differences in persuasive language effectiveness. This approach can offer a broader perspective on the role of persuasive language in election campaigns and facilitate the identification of political industry in best practices.

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